

SI Appendix

Discovering and protecting cryptic biodiversity: a case study of a previously undescribed, vulnerable bird species in Japan

Takema Saitoh^{1,#,*}, Daria Shipilina^{2,#}, Canwei Xia^{2,3}, Lijun Zhang^{2,3}, Shin-Ichi Seki⁴, Urban Olsson^{5,6}, Per Alström^{2,7*}

¹Yamashina Institute for Ornithology, 115 Konoyama, Abiko, Chiba 270-1145, Japan

²Animal Ecology, Department of Ecology and Genetics, Evolutionary Biology Centre, Uppsala University, Norbyvägen 18 D, SE-752 36 Uppsala, Sweden

³Ministry of Education Key Laboratory for Biodiversity and Ecological Engineering, College of Life Sciences, Beijing Normal University, Beijing 100875, China

⁴Kansai Research Center, Forestry and Forest Products Research Institute, Nagaikyutaro 68, Kyoto 612-0855, Japan

⁵Systematics and Biodiversity, Gothenburg University, Department of Zoology, Box 463, SE-405 30 Göteborg, Sweden

⁶Gothenburg Global Biodiversity Centre, Box 461, SE-405 30 Gothenburg, Sweden

⁷Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100101, China

*Corresponding authors: Takema Saitoh saitoh@yamashina.or.jp, and Per Alström per.alstrom@ebc.uu.se (ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7182-2763>). #These two authors contributed equally.

Index

1. Introduction: leaf warblers	3
2. Materials and methods	4
2.1. Field work and sampling	4
2.2. Morphology	4
2.3. Vocalizations	5
2.3.1. Sound collection	5
2.3.2. Measurements	5
2.3.3. Data analysis	6
2.4. DNA	6
2.4.1. Read mapping, SNP calling and filtering approach	6
2.4.2. Phylogenetic analysis of whole-genome SNP data	8
2.4.3. Phylogenetic analysis of genome-wide introns	9
2.4.4. Phylogenetic analysis of mitochondrial DNA	9
3. Results and Discussion	10
3.1. Morphology	10
3.2. Vocalizations	11
3.3. DNA	12
4. Description of a new species	13
4.1. Diagnosis of species	13
4.2. Description of holotype	14
4.3. Morphological variation	15
4.4. Molt	16
4.5. Etymology	16
4.6. Nomenclatural acts	16
4.7. Behaviour	16
4.8. Habitat	17
4.9. Migration	17
4.11. Breeding	17
4.12. Food	18
4.13. Conservation	18
5. References	18
6. SI Appendix Tables	24
7. SI Appendix Figures	45

1. Introduction: leaf warblers

The leaf warblers in the family Phylloscopidae (sensu Alström et al. 2006, Fregin et al. 2012) occur across much of the Old World. Approximately 75% of the species breed in continental Eurasia and adjacent islands (Japan, Sakhalin, Hainan, Canary Islands), with many of these being long-distance migrants (Bairlein et al. 2006, Sokolovskis et al. 2018, AviList Core Team 2025). Nearly 20% of the species are resident in the West Pacific archipelagos (Philippines, Indonesia to Solomon Islands), with nearly all of these species in one comparatively recently diverged clade (Alström et al. 2018; Fig. 2C). Less than 10% of the species are resident in the Afrotropics (with one extending its range to southern Arabia) (Bairlein et al. 2006, AviList Core Team 2025). The leaf warblers are small insectivorous birds that are notorious for often being hard to identify by appearance but more easily separable by song (Ticehurst 1938, Williamson 1967, Alström & Ranft 2003, Bairlein et al. 2006). A multilocus phylogeny comprising all species was recently published, in which the traditional genus *Seicercus* was nested within *Phylloscopus*, and *Seicercus* was separated into two non-sister clades, resulting in synonymization of *Seicercus* with *Phylloscopus* (Alström et al. 2018). The species taxonomy has changed dramatically in the past three decades, with the number of recognised species rising from 52 in the mid-1980s (Watson et al. 1986, *Phylloscopus* and *Seicercus* combined) to 77 species at present (all placed in *Phylloscopus*; AviList Core Team 2025). Only six of the presently recognised species have been described as newly discovered in this period: *P. hainanus* (Olsson et al. 1993), *P. emeiensis* (Alström & Olsson 1995), *P. soror* (originally placed in *Seicercus*; Alström & Olsson 1999, Alström & Olsson 2000), *P. omeiensis* (originally placed in *Seicercus*; Martens et al. 1999), *P. calciatilis* (Alström et al. 2010) and *P. rotiensis* (Ng et al. 2018). Two other taxa have been described in the past decade, but are presently treated as subspecies (AviList Core Team 2025): *P. suaramerdu* and *P. emilsalimi* (Rheindt et al. 2020). In other words, the main reason for the sharp increase in the number of species is not the result of new species being discovered, but instead is due to studies of, especially, vocalizations and DNA, which have elevated multiple subspecies to species rank (see reviews in Rheindt 2006, Martens 2010 and Alström et al. 2018).

Phylloscopus ijimae was described from Miyakejima in the Izu Islands in 1892 (Stejneger 1892). It breeds in two disjunct Japanese archipelagos: the Izu Islands southeast of the largest Japanese island, Honshu, and the Tokara Islands, in the Nansei Shoto or Ryukyu Islands, southwest of Kyushu. In the Izu Islands, Higuchi (1973) observed *P. ijimae* during the breeding season on 10 islands (Oshima, Toshima, Nijima, Shikinejima, Kozushima, Miyakejima, Mikurajima, Hachijojjima, Hachijohkojima and Aogashima), but during a recent survey, breeding individuals were not observed on Oshima, Shikinejima and Aogashima (Ueta & Sato 2021). The Tokara Islands population was only discovered in 1988 on the island of Nakanoshima (Higuchi & Kawaji 1989), and has been observed during the breeding season also on Kuchinoshima, Tairajima, Suwanosejima and Akusekijima (Higuchi & Kawaji 1989, Seki et al. 2011, The Ornithological Society of Japan 2012, Seki 2024) (Fig. 1A). The species is believed to winter in the Philippines, and migrants have been observed on Honshu, Mishima, Shikoku, Kyushu,

Yakushima, Amami-Oshima, Okinawajima, Miyakejima and Yaeyama Island (The Ornithological Society of Japan 2012). The phylogeny by Alström et al. (2018) recovered *P. ijimae* as sister to Eastern Crowned Warbler *P. coronatus*, which breeds allopatrically on the main Japanese islands and on continental East Asia and winters in Southeast Asia (Clement 2020a), and these in turn formed a sister clade to Lemon-throated Leaf Warbler *P. cebuensis* and Philippine Leaf Warbler *P. olivaceus*, which are resident in the Philippines (Clement 2020b, c).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Field work and sampling

On 10–14 June 2017, T.S., P.A. and U.O. visited Nakanoshima in the Tokara Islands with the specific goal to study *P. ijimae*; S.-I.S. had already been there over 100 times since 1996, as well as several times to four of the other Tokara Islands. All of us had previous experience with this species from Miyakejima in the Izu Islands, S.-I.S. also from three of the other Izu Islands. On our visit in June 2017, *P. ijimae* was one of the commonest birds on Nakanoshima, and we collected two specimens (with DNA samples), eight additional blood samples, and sound recordings of song from 29 males and of calls from six individuals, which we could compare to data already collected from Miyakejima.

2.2. Morphology

A total of 50 live adult males of *P. ijimae* were measured from Tokara Is. (Nakanoshima Is., 35), Izu Is. (Miyakejima, 8; Hachijojima, 4; Aogashima, 2; and Mikurajima, 1), Japan between 2010 and 2023 (SI Appendix Table S13). Using digital calipers (Mitsutoyo, CD-15PM, Tajima Black-15), we measured natural wing length (wing chord; NW), tail length (with a ruler inserted between the two central rectrices; TAIL), tarsus length (following Pyle et al. 1987; TAR), bill length from the anterior end of the nostril to the tip of the bill; BL), and total head length (from tip of bill to back of head; TH). All measurements were taken by T.S. and S.-I.S.

To detect external morphological differences between Tokara and Izu Is. populations, we tested for statistically significant differences between mean values for each of the measurements using Mac Statistical Analysis ver. 2.0 (Esumi, Tokyo, Japan). In addition, we performed Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using Mac EXCEL Multivariate Analysis ver. 1.0b (Esumi). The five characteristics included in the PCA were NW, TAIL, TAR, BL and TH. The principal component scores were extracted from the correlation matrix.

2.3. Vocalizations

2.3.1. Sound collection

Sound recordings were obtained from both our own collections and from xeno-canto (xeno-canto.org) and Macaulay Library (macaulaylibrary.org). For multiple recordings from online sound databases collected on the same day at the same location by the same person, we only analyzed song types that were clearly different from each other. Recordings with background noise or strong reverberation that affected taking measurements were excluded. Songs from 33 individuals from the Izu Islands (Miyakejima, one from Hachijojima) and 29 individuals from the Tokara Islands were selected for analysis (SI Appendix Table S14). In addition, calls from six individuals from the Izu Islands (Miyakejima, one from Hachijojima) and five individuals from the Tokara Islands were selected for analysis (SI Appendix Table S14).

2.3.2. Measurements

See SI Appendix Fig. S15 for the sound terminology used. Sonograms were created in Raven Pro 1.6.5 (Cornell Lab of Ornithology, USA), with the following settings: Window size = 132 samples, window type = Hamming, 3 dB filter bandwidth = 473 Hz, Time Grid overlap = 0%, Time Grid Hop Size = 132 samples, Frequency Grid DFT Size 256 samples, Frequency Grid Spacing 172 Hz.

The songs could be clearly separated into two main types, Type I and Type II, which were treated separately (see Results). For both these song types, the following eight variables were measured in each strophe (SI Appendix Fig. S15): Low Frequency (=minimum frequency, Hz), High Frequency (=maximum frequency, Hz), Center Frequency (the frequency that divides the selection into two frequency intervals of equal energy, Hz), Delta Frequency (=frequency span, Hz), Bandwidth 90% (=the difference between Frequency 5% and Frequency 95% [Frequency 5% = the frequency that divides the selection into two frequency intervals containing 5% and 95% of the energy in the selection; the summed energy has to exceed 5%. Frequency 95% = same as Frequency 5% except that the summed energy has to exceed 95%], Hz; see Charif et al. 2010 for further details), Delta Time (=duration, s), Duration 90% (=the difference between Time 5% and Time 95% [Time 5% = the point in time that divides the selection into two time intervals containing 5% and 95% of the energy in the selection; the summed energy has to exceed 5% of the total energy. Time 95% = same as Time 5% except that the summed energy has to exceed 95% of the total energy.], s; see Charif et al. 2010 for further details), and Average Entropy (=describes the amount of disorder for a typical spectrum within the selection, bits). Any harmonics were not included in the measurements (these were rare, and were mainly believed to be caused by overloading of the recording signal). In addition, we noted the total number of syllables within the strophe, as well as the number of distinct elements within a syllable, and also

calculated the number of syllables per second, both using the Delta Time and Duration 90% measurements.

Each main song type (Type I, Type II; see Results) contained several variations composed of different syllables (strophe types); in some cases, a single recording contained a single strophe type that was repeated multiple times, but in other cases several different strophe types were alternated between. All different strophe types per recording were measured, and 10 strophes per strophe type per recording, or all strophes if fewer than 10 for a particular strophe type. In total, 130 strophes from Type I songs and 45 strophes from Type II songs were measured.

For the calls ($n = 13$), the same variables as for songs were measured except the number of syllables and elements, which are not applicable.

All measurements were taken by the same person (P.A.).

2.3.3. Data analysis

First, we calculated mean values for each strophe type from each individual, mainly to account for the fact that the number of repetitions of a syllable sometimes varied among strophes of the same type in the same recording. Then we used these mean values to compare the song differences between recordings from Tokara and Izu islands. We also visually inspected sonograms of all of these recordings. The same approach was taken for the calls. The appropriateness of the classification of the songs into two main types (see Results) based on visual inspection of sonograms was evaluated using Discriminant Function Analysis (DFA), with leave-one-out cross validation (where each recording was assigned to a geographical area based on discriminant functions calculated from all recordings except the one being classified). MANOVA was used to assess the overall differences between individuals from Tokara and Izu, followed by an independent sample t-test for each variable. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with varimax rotation was used to compress the original variables into independent principal components (with Eigenvalues >1), and DFA was used to determine whether the individuals from Tokara and Izu could be distinguished. Results from leave-one-out cross validation are reported as percentages of individuals correctly assigned in DFA. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 21.0 (IBM Corp., USA). Data were presented as the mean \pm standard deviation. Differences with P values of less than 0.05 were considered significant.

2.4. DNA

2.4.1. Read mapping, SNP calling and filtering approach

Bioinformatic analysis for the main dataset (dataset #1) was conducted for 14 individuals representing two island populations. Sample preparation and sequencing approach described in

the main text. Adapter trimming and quality filtering were done using Trimmomatic v. 0.36 (Bolger et al. 2014) which removed adapter sequences, low-quality reads (those with over 50% of bases having Phred quality scores <3), and poly-N reads (those with $\geq 3\%$ unidentified nucleotides). Trimmed reads were aligned to the *Phylloscopus trochilus* genome reference (Lundberg et al 2023) (1) using BWA 0.7.19 (Li & Durbin 2009), with output SAM files subsequently converted to BAM format, sorted, indexed, and quantified for mapping statistics (SI Appendix Table S15) using Samtools (Li et al. 2009).

For each individual, variants were called using the HaplotypeCaller tool from GATK to produce gVCF (genomic VCF) files. This process allows for the inclusion of information on variant and invariant sites. During the next step – index creation with GenomeDBI – gVCF files were split into 19 regions of approximately similar genomic length to increase computational efficiency. Three short contigs appeared to be corrupted and were omitted (VHQE01000468.1:1-4419761, VHQE01000216.1:1-28090684, VHQE01000163.1:1-4298493), due to their short length we do not expect this step to influence any of the subsequent results or analyses. Individual vcf files were jointly called using the GATK GenotypeGVCF tool with standard settings allowing for the calling of invariant sites. We refer to the resulting SNP set as dataset #1.

To prepare the dataset for future analyses we applied hard filtering to the raw VCF files as a replacement for the variant quality score recalibration (VQSR) method outlined in the GATK Best Practices (Van Der Auwera & O’Connor 2020). We excluded low-quality sites using bcftools v1.15 (Li 2011) using following criteria: variant quality by depth ($QD < 2.0$), Fisher's strand bias ($FS > 60.0$), root mean square mapping quality ($MQ < 40.0$), U-based Z-approximation from the Rank Sum Test for mapping qualities ($MQRankSum < -12.5$), and U-based Z-approximation from the Rank Sum Test for read position ($ReadPosRankSum < -8.0$). Following this, indels and multiallelic sites were excluded (`--exclude-types indels,other --max-alleles 2`), and the refined VCF file was reindexed.

Quality control of hard filtered variant calling sites was performed using summary statistics from vcftools (Danecek et al. 2011) and tailored Python scripts. To determine the quality of our VCF files, we utilized metrics such as allele frequency (`--freq2`), depth of coverage (`--depth`), average depth across sites (`--site-mean-depth`), quality metrics for each site (`--site-quality`), individual sample missingness (`--missing-indv`), site-specific missingness (`--missing-site`), and estimates of heterozygosity (`--het`). Following the summary statistics analysis, we set filters to apply to both variant and invariant sites. In order to do this, we split the vcf files and applied following filters: for variant sites we used per individual missingness (`--max-missing-count 0`, no missing data tolerated), minimum variant quality (`--minQ 20`) and maximum average depth (`--max-meanDP 40`), invariant sites we used more stringent criteria setting minimum and maximum depth (`--min-meanDP 10`, `--max-meanDP 30`). Following the filtering step, the vcf files were merged using bcftools concat.

Using the enhanced Sarek Nextflow pipeline (Garcia et al. 2020), we performed rapid SNP calling on individuals from sister and outgroup species (dataset #2). Initially, the Sarek pipeline assessed the quality of raw reads using FastQC (version 0.11.9; Andrews 2010). The reads were rigorously trimmed with fastp (Chen et al. 2018) to eliminate (1) sequences at the 5 and 3 ends (12 bp and 3 bp, respectively), (2) adaptor sequences, (3) reads of low quality (overall Phred score < 30), and (4) short reads (< 30 bp). Post-trimming, read quality was reassessed using FastQC. Subsequently, reads were aligned to the reference genome via BWA-MEM (version 0.7.17; Li 2013), followed by sorting and indexing with SAMtools (version 1.9; Li et al. 2009). An average of 96.7% of reads were successfully mapped to the reference genome (SI Appendix Table S16). Optical and PCR duplicate reads were identified using GATK MarkDuplicates (version 4.1.4.1; DePristo et al. 2011), and these duplicates, along with reads of low mapping quality (MAPQ < 30), were filtered out using SAMtools. The base quality score recalibration (BQSR) step within the Sarek pipeline is omitted. Variant calling was performed using the HaplotypeCaller tool from the GATK suite within the Sarek pipeline. Total unfiltered file included: 101,840,763 variants. We refer to this SNP set as dataset #2.

We applied the same hard filtering approach to dataset #2 as described above and obtained the same summary statistics. Based on those, we choose soft filtering criteria for the dataset #2: --minQ 20, --max-meanDP 50, --min-meanDP 10, --minGQ 30, --minDP 7, --maxDP 56, which allowed a stringent control for data quality (minQ - minimum quality filter, minGQ - minimum genotype quality) and exclusion of potential effect of uneven sequencing coverage (filters for maximum and minimum absolute and mean depth).

2.4.2. Phylogenetic analysis of whole-genome SNP data

For phylogenetic reconstruction, we utilized dataset #2 and employed SNAPPER, a Bayesian methodology implemented in BEAST2 for inferring species trees and demographics from unlinked binary markers using diffusion models of allele frequency dynamics (Stoltz et al 2020). We inferred relationships within the “*P. coronatus* clade” (which includes *P. ijimae*) using whole-genome SNP data and created three thinningschemes: sampling SNPs separated by 20kb (# SNP = 34,143), 50kb (# SNP = 15,830), and 100kb (# SNP = 8,488). All thinned vcf files were converted into binary nexus alignment files, using the python script vcf2phylip.py ([\[https://github.com/edgardomortiz/vcf2phylip\]](https://github.com/edgardomortiz/vcf2phylip))(<https://github.com/edgardomortiz/vcf2phylip>).

XML input file for BEAST2 was prepared using BEAUti v2.7.6 assuming the GTR+G+I model and a Yule tree prior. We tested both strict and uncorrelated log-normal relaxed clock models to account for rate variation among lineages (Drummond et al. 2006) and ran Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) analysis for 10 million generations, sampling every 1,000 generations. Convergence was assessed in Tracer v1.7.2 (Rambaut et al. 2018), ensuring ESS > 200. Multiple

independent runs confirmed convergence. Consensus maximum clade credibility trees were generated in TreeAnnotator (v2.7.6) and visualized in FigTree (v1.4.4) (Rambaut et al. 2018).

For the three SNP datasets, preliminary runs converged on identical tree topologies after ~1 million iterations. We therefore terminated analyses for the two smaller datasets and extended the run for the largest dataset (34,143 SNPs) until full convergence. This run was repeated with two additional random seeds, producing consistent topologies. A representative tree was summarized in DensiTree and used for the final figure.

To test the effect of unequal sampling, we repeated the analysis on the largest dataset using two random subsampling schemes (two individuals from *P. coronatus* and two from each *P. ijimae* population). Both non-overlapping subsamples produced topologies consistent with the full dataset.

2.4.3. Phylogenetic analysis of genome-wide introns

To reconstruct the global *Phylloscopus* tree we further used the BirdScanner pipeline (Ericson et al. 2020) (github.com/Naturhistoriska/birdscanner) to extract sequence homologs of intronic loci from fasta sequences compiled for each individual sample. As references we used alignments from four passerine species (Rifleman *Acanthisitta chloris*, American Crow *Corvus brachyrhynchos*, Medium Ground-Finch *Geospiza fortis*, and Golden-collared Manakin *Manacus vitellinus*) generated by Jarvis et al. (2014) and previously used by Jiang et al. (2024). For each sample, the parsed-out sequence was placed in a fasta file compiling the orthologs of respective locus. These resulting fasta files were processed with ATPW – Align-and-Trees-Parallel-Workflow, <https://github.com/nylander/Align-and-trees-parallel-workflow>, which first aligned all sets of orthologous genes with Mafft v.7.526 (Katoh et al. 2002, Katoh & Standley 2013). The alignments were then filtered with BMGE v.1.12 (Criscuolo & Gribaldo 2010) which selects regions in a multiple sequence alignment that are suited for phylogenetic inference. Phylogenetic trees for each filtered locus were inferred with ParGenes (Morel et al. 2019) and RAxML-NG, (Kozlov et al. 2019), filtered with TreeShrink (Uyen & Mirarab 2018) and realigned with Mafft. Substitution model selection was performed using ModelTest-NG (Flouri et al. 2014, Darriba et al. 2020) and phylogenetic trees for each locus were inferred for these filtered and realigned alignments with RAxML-NG and ParGenes. Finally, a species tree was estimated from the individual trees using the weighted ASTRAL algorithm implemented in ASTER (Zhang & Mirarab 2022).

2.4.4. Phylogenetic analysis of mitochondrial DNA

We used the same approach to phylogenetic reconstruction for two sample sets (whole *Phylloscopus* tree $n = 71$ and all *P. ijimae* tree $n = 35$) with mitochondrial DNA. An alignment of the *cytochrome b* (cytb) gene (1,041 base pairs) was created using SeaView v. 5.05 (Gouy et al. 2010). Bayesian phylogenetic inference was performed using BEAST 2.7.8, configured via

BEAUti to set up substitution models, clock, and tree priors. Sequence evolution was modeled using the GTR + Γ (4 categories) substitution model with empirical base frequencies. A strict molecular clock with a single rate across the tree and a Yule speciation prior were applied. Two independent MCMC chains of 10 million generations each were run, sampling every 1,000 steps, with a 10 % burn-in. Chain convergence and adequate mixing (ESS > 200) were confirmed using Tracer v1.7.1. Log and tree outputs were combined using LogCombiner (BEAST toolkit) and summarized into a maximum clade credibility (MCC) tree with mean node heights using TreeAnnotator. Final visualization of phylogenetic trees was conducted in FigTree v1.4.4.

Whole mitochondrial genomes (16,941 base pairs) were extracted from BAM files produced at the read mapping step described in 2.4.1. We utilized *samtools consensus* to generate a consensus sequence of the whole mitochondrial genome (specified by the reference CM046213.1:1-16942), applying a minimum depth of 7 for consensus calling, ensuring the inclusion of deletions and insertions as part of the consensus sequence. This method facilitated the accurate and efficient extraction of mitochondrial sequences for further analysis. We aligned genomes using MAFFT (FFT-NS-2 algorithm). The phylogenetic analysis was repeated using Bayesian (BEAST) methods described above.

Published *cytb* sequences were also downloaded from GenBank. The origin of all *cytb* sequences and their GenBank numbers are in SI Appendix Table S14.

Uncorrected (p) pairwise genetic distances for *cytb* were calculated in MEGA 12.1 (Kumar et al. 2025): uniform rates among sites, homogeneous pattern among lineages, complete deletion of missing data (latter following Fregin et al. 2012).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Morphology

Morphometrics for 50 adult males are presented in SI Appendix Table S2. The mean for each measurement was slightly larger in the Izu Is. population than in the Tokara one, but only TAR (Welch's test, $p < 0.001$) and TH (Welch's test, $p < 0.05$) showed statistically significant differences. The trend in morphological differences between the two populations is the same as found by Seki (2024). The PCA did not show any clear morphological differences between the two populations (SI Appendix Fig. S1, and SI Appendix Table S1). The contributions of the principal components PC1, PC2, and PC3 were 49.7%, 19.1%, and 16.2%, respectively. For PC1, the top four factor loadings were related to body size, and larger positive values indicated larger body size. By contrast, on PC2, larger values indicated longer TH and TAR. No plumage differences could be detected between specimens from Tokara and Izu Islands.

3.2. Vocalizations

The song could be clearly separated into two main types, Type I and Type II. Only six strophes (out of 174) that were classified based on their sound and visual inspection of sonograms were suggested to be misclassified based on the DFA; four of these were moved to the suggested category whereas two were retained in the original category. The two main types were sometimes combined in a strophe in separate blocks (SI Appendix Fig. S2). Type I (Fig. 1D–I, G–L, SI Appendix Fig. S2, SI Appendix Table 3), which was by far the commonest one, was a rattling repetition of a mono- or di-syllabic note (syllable), which was usually rather complex as seen in a sonogram; the song usually gradually increased in strength (amplitude) during the first few syllables and then dropped a little in strength at the very end (on sonograms, the first few syllables were often too faint to be seen when the contrast was set so that the later syllables were neatly visible and not forming black smears). The vast majority of the Type I strophes consisted of a single syllable type, and very few strophes had two syllable types arranged in separate blocks. Many of the recordings had a single syllable type repeated multiple times (up to 44 times, ML 647192010), with slight variation only in the number of syllables in each strophe, whereas in other recordings there was an alternation between different strophe types (up to eight different types in a single recording from Tokara [ML 647191965] and up to seven types in a single recording from Izu [XC749102]). Type II songs (Fig. 1M–P, SI Appendix Fig. S2, SI Appendix Table 03 usually consisted of simple, soft, “smooth” (i.e. not rapidly frequency modulated, not “jagged”) syllables, which were usually more drawn-out and softer-sounding than the Type I syllables; the number of syllables was on average lower than in Type I, and unlike in Type I, many syllables consisted of two different-looking and different-sounding elements.

For Type I songs, there were significant differences between Tokara and Izu (MANOVA: Pillai’s Trace = 0.92, $F_{12,49} = 48.23$, $P < 0.001$), and all individual variables differed significantly between the two islands (SI Appendix Table S3). Importantly, the syllables in Tokara songs invariably consisted of single elements (although this was sometimes only apparent at high contrast, when two seemingly separate elements were shown to be thinly connected at the bottom or top), whereas the mean number of elements per syllable in Izu was 1.9 (± 0.3 s.d.). Only a fraction of the sonograms had extremely similar syllables in Tokara and Izu. The PCA generated three principal components with eigenvalues >1.0 , explaining in total 81.0 % of the variance (SI Appendix Table S4). In plots of the three first principal components, the recordings from Tokara and Izu formed largely separated clusters along PC1, with considerably more overlap along the other axes (Fig 1H, SI Appendix Fig. S3). In contrast, in the DFA, 100% of the recordings from Tokara and 97% of the ones from Izu were correctly classified (SI Appendix Table S5). Audibly, the songs from Tokara sounded on average lower-pitched and faster (i.e. more syllables per time unit in a strophe) than the ones from Izu.

Also for Type II songs, there were significant differences between Tokara and Izu (MANOVA: Pillai's Trace = 0.828, $F_{11,33} = 14.455$, $P < 0.001$). Independent sample t-test showed higher frequency and entropy in Type II songs from Izu than from Tokara (SI Appendix Table S6). Visual inspection of sonograms revealed that the Type II songs generally had a simpler structure in Tokara, with elements either rather gently up- or down-sloping or V-shaped, whereas in Izu many of the individual elements had a more complex structure (Fig. 1M–P, SI Appendix Fig. S2). A PCA revealed some overlap between the two groups, whereas in a DFA, 90% of the Type II songs from Tokara and 92% of the ones from Izu were correctly classified (SI Appendix Tables S7, S8, SI Appendix Fig. S4).

The call is a short, thin whistle that usually sounds slightly descending in pitch, *tsee(u)* (SI Appendix Fig. S5). No significant differences were found between Tokara and Izu; it is possible that larger samples (now only 5 and 6, respectively) would have revealed significant differences, as Delta Frequency/Bandwidth 90% were nearly significantly different (SI Appendix Fig. S6, SI Appendix Table S9). Sonograms differed in being mainly rather evenly descending in Tokara, while they were usually either of rather even pitch, slightly bent up-down, or even slightly rising in pitch in Izu; larger sample sizes are needed to test whether these differences hold or not.

Playback tests have often been used in taxonomic studies (e.g., Alström & Olsson 1992, Alström et al. 1997, Alström & Olsson 1999, Freeman & Montgomery 2017, Singh et al. 2020). However, as discussed by, e.g. Alström & Olsson (1992), results from playback tests using songs from allopatric populations should be interpreted cautiously. Songs from allopatric taxa, which the tested taxon likely has never encountered, may still elicit a response if they are sufficiently similar to the tested song. However, the absence of a response to foreign songs – despite a strong response to conspecific songs – is more taxonomically informative (of high relevance with sympatric taxa).

3.3. DNA

Trees based on mitochondrial DNA have often been found to be incongruent with trees based on nuclear DNA, and mitochondrial divergence has been suggested to potentially have other causes than population divergence (e.g., Irwin 2002, Spottiswoode et al. 2011, Zhang et al. 2019, Zhang et al. 2024). However, the congruence in the present study between the mtDNA tree and the trees based on genome-wide SNPs and introns supports that all of them represent the species phylogeny in this case.

Although it is not entirely clear whether F_{ST} values calculated in different studies are directly comparable (cf. the genetic distances often used in taxonomic studies of birds, which are not directly comparable; see Fregin et al. 2012), the difference between the two *P. ijimae* populations was considerably higher than within-species divergence. However, as F_{ST} measures

the intrapopulation variation in relation to the interpopulation divergence, the extremely low intrapopulation variation in both *P. ijimae* populations (0.003 and 0.002 for Tokara and Izu, respectively; SI Appendix Fig. S11 C, D) will have inflated the F_{ST} comparison between them.

4. Description of a new species

Based on the distinctness of the Tokara population in relation to the Izu population in multiple independent traits, we describe the previously unnamed Tokara islands population as a species new to science, for which we propose the name

Phylloscopus tokaraensis, sp. nov.

Tokara Leaf Warbler

Holotype. Yamashina Institute for Ornithology No. YIO-76774, adult male, Nakanoshima Island, Tokara Islands, Japan, collected on 10 June 2017 by Takema Saitoh, Per Alström and Urban Olsson. Saved as both a study skin and a skeleton, prepared by Yasuko Iwami: <https://decochan.net/index.php?p=2&o=ssp&id=75238>. Photos of the same individual alive are in Figure 1 and in Macaulay Library (SI Appendix Table S18). GenBank number for the mitochondrial cytochrome b gene: PX738503.

Paratype: Yamashina Institute for Ornithology No. YIO-76875, adult male, collected on the same day at the same place: <https://decochan.net/index.php?p=2&o=ssp&id=75820>. Photos of the same individual alive are in Macaulay Library (SI Appendix Table S18). GenBank number for the mitochondrial cytochrome b gene: PX738504.

4.1. Diagnosis of species

Phylloscopus tokaraensis and *P. ijimae* are characterized by the uniformly greyish crown, lacking darker or paler stripes; mainly whitish underparts with contrastingly pale yellow undertail-coverts; narrow pale tips to the greater coverts, forming a thin, sometimes very indistinct, pale wing-bar; and pale orange lower mandible. Easily distinguishable from *P. coronatus* by the uniformly coloured crown; from *P. borealis*, *P. examinandus* and *P. xanthodryas* by the less distinct pale supercilium and narrower and less contrasting dark stripe on the ear-coverts behind the eye, whiter underparts with contrastingly pale yellow undertail-coverts, and pale orange lower mandible (usually prominent dark tip in *P. borealis*, *P. examinandus* and *P. xanthodryas* but rarely entirely orange); and from *P. borealoides* and *P. tenellipes* by the greener upperparts, paler crown which does not contrast strongly with the mantle (crown clearly contrastingly darker and greyer than mantle in *P. borealoides* and *P. tenellipes*), less prominent pale supercilium and dark stripe through the eye, contrastingly pale yellow undertail-coverts, pale orange lower mandible (prominent dark tip in *P. borealoides* and *P. tenellipes*), and darker tarsus, toes and claws (pale pinkish in *P. borealoides* and *P. tenellipes*);

the wing-bars are variable in *P. borealoides* and *P. tenellipes*, but they often show rather distinct, buffy wing-bars on both the median and greater coverts.

Phylloscopus tokaraensis is not diagnosably different from *P. ijimae* by morphology. In the mitochondrial cytochrome b gene, at least 50 positions have fixed differences between these two species (order: Tokara Islands [Nakanoshima]/Izu Islands [Miyakejima, Hachiojima, Mikurajima; Kagoshima on migration]; alignment in SI Appendix Fig. S16, and positions based on that): position 52 T/C, 90 T/C, 105 C/T, 138 C/T, 150 C/T, 156 C/T, 162 C/A, 261 G/A, 264 A/G, 339 C/T, 384 G/A, 414 C/T, 417 T/C, 420 T/C, 423 G/A, 453 C/T, 456 A/C, 463 G/C, 474 G/A, 498 T/C, 537 C/A, 543 T/C, 546 T/C, 570 T/C, 576 C/T, 585 T/C, 609 A/G, 612 C/T, 618 C/T, 623 C/G, 625 T/C, 636 C/T, 654 G/A, 666 C/T, 690 C/T, 696 A/G, 699 G/A, 723 T/C, 726 G/A, 768 C/A, 816 C/T, 819 A/G, 825 C/T, 828 A/C, 835 T/C, 846 A/G, 861 A/C, 870 T/C, 888 G/C, 891 C/T.

By tying our diagnosis to specific positions in a gene, we adhere to the recommendations by the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (Rheindt et al. 2023).

4.2. Description of holotype

Plumage: Head and body, tertials and probably lesser and median and inner greater upperwing-coverts rather fresh; rest of wing, and tail moderately worn. Forehead, crown, nape (including sides), mantle, scapulars, back, rump and uppertail-coverts pale green with a slight greyish tinge, most noticeable on the crown. Long, narrow supercilium from approximately halfway between tip of forehead feathering and base of gape of bill to slightly beyond rear end of ear-coverts; whitish with faint yellowish tinge, especially above eye. Lores fairly dark greyish, forming a dark stripe. Upper part of ear-coverts, behind eye same colour as crown, lower part of ear-coverts behind and below eye slightly paler with faint yellowish tinge, with diffuse paler (almost whitish) spot at rear end; darker upper part of ear-coverts form a rather poorly contrasting dark eye-stripe on rear ear-coverts; whitish crescent below eye (broken in front and at rear by dark stripe through eye). Throat, breast, belly and flanks whitish with indistinct pale yellowish streaking, especially on centre of belly, and slightly greenish breast-sides. Undertail-coverts pale yellow. Lesser and median upperwing-coverts have medium grey-brown centres and pale green tips; appear rather uniformly green like mantle. Greater upperwing-coverts have medium grey-brown inner webs (usually concealed on closed wing) and paler and greener outer webs, with poorly defined narrow even paler and greener outer edges; very narrow and indistinct whitish tips to outermost five (six) greater upperwing-coverts forming very narrow pale wing-bar. Tertials brownish-grey with greenish tinge and narrow, poorly defined paler green outer edge (tertials not contrasting much with upperparts). Alula and primary coverts basically similar to greater upperwing-coverts but lacking paler tips. Remiges medium grey-brown with narrow fairly clear-cut yellowish-green edges to outer webs (slightly brighter than, and contrasting with, upperparts), which reach to emarginations on emarginated outer primaries (see below) and almost to tips on other remiges; narrow whitish edges to inner webs of remiges. Underwing-

coverts and axillaries whitish with faint yellowish tinge, especially along leading edge of wing. Rectrices medium grey-brown with narrow yellowish-green outer edges (slightly brighter than, and contrasting with, upperparts) and very narrow, slightly diffuse whitish inner edges to four outer pairs of feathers (very indistinct on third and fourth outermost pairs counted centrifugally).

Bare parts: Upper mandible dark grey with narrow pale orange cutting edge (more distinct basally than distally); lower mandible and gape flanges pale orange. Tarsus rather dark brown-grey, toes marginally paler and browner, claws brown-grey, toe pads rather pale brownish-orange. Iris dark grey-brown, hardly contrasting with iris. Orbital ring dark grey.

Structure: Bill relatively long and strong with slightly hooked tip to upper mandible. Nostril elongated, slightly kidney-shaped. Three fairly distinct, and a few less distinct, thin rictal bristles above gape. Claws short, decurved. Outer 3–4 (at least) secondaries have slightly “spike shaped” tips. Measurements (mm): NW 59.8, TAIL 40.6, TAR 15.7, BL 7.37, bill length from tip to skull 16.0 and TH 30.1. Wing formula (primaries, P, numbered descendantly, measurements in mm, to nearest 0.5 mm): Wing tip, P7=P8, P9 –6.2, P10 –35.0 (+3.0 in relation to tips of primary coverts), P6 –0.5, P5 –5.5, P4 –8.0, P3 –10.0, P2 –11.5, P1 –15.0. P6–P8 emarginated on outer webs, P5 weakly emarginated on outer web.

4.3. Morphological variation

Plumage: Slight plumage variation, cf. photos on Macaulay Library, Nos 00–00. The crown can be slightly contrastingly greyer than the mantle, and both the crown and the mantle can be slightly greyer. The supercilium can be slightly more yellow-tinged, especially above and in front of the eye, and can appear almost broken halfway behind the eye. The pale spot on the rear ear-coverts is not always apparent. The pale tips to the greater upperwing-coverts can be more distinct than in the holotype, but also less distinct (because of wear?). The pale edges to the inner webs of the outer rectrices can be very indistinct and pale greyish rather than whitish.

Morphometrics: The variation in morphometrics is given in the table below.

Natural wing length	Tail length	Tarsus length	Bill length from skull	Bill depth	Bill width	Total Head
61.2 ± 1.91	44.7 ± 1.86	18.5 ± 0.44	15.1 ± 0.69	2.9 ± 0.18	3.2 ± 0.14	30.8 ± 0.62

Morphometrics for all samples of *Phylloscopus tokaraensis*. Mean ± standard deviation and span in parenthesis; measurements in mm, measured to nearest 0.5 mm); n = 11 for all measurements.

Wing formula: The variation in wing formula is given in the table below.

P10	P10>p.c.	P9	P8	P7	P6	P5	P4	P3
-----	----------	----	----	----	----	----	----	----

35.2 ± 0.99 (34.0– 37.0; n = 7)	4.1 ± 0.93 (3.0–6.0; n = 7)	6.0 ± 0.80 (5.0– 7.0; n = 8)	0 ± 0 (n = 8)	0 ± 0 (n = 8)	0.8 ± 0.46 (0–1.5; n = 8)	4.9 ± 0.68 (4.0– 6.0; n = 8)	8.8 ± 0.75 (7.5– 10.0; n = 8)	10.9 ± 1.07 (9.0– 12.0; n = 7)
---	--------------------------------------	--	------------------	------------------	------------------------------------	--	---	--

Wing formula for all samples of *Phylloscopus tokaraensis*. Mean ± standard deviation; span and number in parenthesis; measurements in mm, measured to nearest 0.5 mm; P = primary, numbered descendantly, p.c. = primary coverts).

4.4. Molt

Not studied. The birds caught in early June had rather fresh head and body plumage, and probably also lesser and median upperwing-coverts, and moderately worn remiges and rectrices; seven out of ten caught individuals in 2017 also had worn greater upperwing-coverts and tertials, while three had fresh tertials. Based on this, the species was deduced to have undergone a complete post-breeding and a partial pre-breeding molt.

4.5. Etymology

The name refers to the Tokara Islands, where the species breeds.

4.6. Nomenclatural acts

The electronic edition of this article conforms to the requirements of the amended International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (International Commission of Zoological Nomenclature 2012), and hence the new name contained herein is available under that Code from the electronic edition of this article. This published work and the nomenclatural act it contains have been registered in ZooBank, the online registration system for the International Commission of Zoological Nomenclature. The ZooBank Life Science Identifiers (LSIDs) can be resolved and the associated information viewed through any standard web browser by appending the LSID to the prefix “<http://zoobank.org/>”. The LSID for this publication is: [urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:506F06C5-9A19-4147-9F25-C90625B29CDF](http://zoobank.org/pub:506F06C5-9A19-4147-9F25-C90625B29CDF). The electronic edition of this work was published in a journal with ISSN 2752-6542, and has been archived and is available from the digital repository <https://zenodo.org>.

4.7. Behaviour

Forages and sings mainly high in the canopy, but occasionally lower down, even in bamboo.

4.8. Habitat

On Nakanoshima, *P. tokaraensis* occurs in all types of broadleaf subtropical forest, usually with bamboo in the undergrowth, from at least 50–500 m a.s.l. (uncommon above 400 m a.s.l.). It also occurs in mixed broadleaf and black pine *Pinus thunbergii* forest and, uncommonly, in tall dense bamboo stands with scattered trees. The habitat choice seems very similar on Kuchinoshima, Swanosejima, and Akusekijima. Seki (2024) reports that the vegetation at nest sites ($n = 37$) was mostly tall forest with a dense understory of bamboo *Pleioblastus linearis* (94.6%), while the upper story was evergreen broadleaf forest dominated by *Castanopsis sieboldii* (48.6%), or mixed coniferous–evergreen broadleaf forest dominated by *Pinus thunbergii* (43.2%), and *Cryptomeria japonica* plantation (2.7 %). Two nests (5.4%) were found in *Pleioblastus linearis* thickets adjacent to tall forest or with scattered evergreen broadleaf trees, and never in continuous large Ryukyu bamboo stands.

4.9 Migration

The following is based mainly on Seki et al. (2011) and Harada et al. (2019). On Nakanoshima, there are a few records from February, with an increase in March, and common occurrence from April to August. The timing of the autumn migration is unclear, as there have been few surveys after September. The winter quarters are unknown. Some of the records during the migration period could potentially have been of *P. ijimae (sensu stricto)*, which probably migrates through this area.

4.11. Breeding

The following is based on Seki (2024, in Japanese), based on 37 nests found on Nakanoshima. Most of the nests were built in bamboo *Pleioblastus linearis*, with one nest in a broadleaf shrub *Eurya japonica* and one on a thick vine (species unknown) hanging from a tall tree. All nests were spherical in shape, and mainly made of dead bamboo leaves, with other materials including dead leaves of broadleaf trees (45.9%), ferns (13.5%), thin roots (5.4%), and Japanese black pine *Pinus thunbergii* (2.7%). Nest linings were made of dead broadleaf leaves with only the veins remaining ($n = 22$), with other materials including feathers (18.2%), thin roots (4.5%), and dead leaves of Japanese black pine (4.5%). The nests were placed 1.0 to 5.0 m (mean 3.2 m) above the ground. For the 22 nests for which the size could be measured, the major axis was 16.0 ± 2.8 cm (mean \pm SD), the minor axis was 12.4 ± 1.9 cm, and the entrance was located either above, diagonally above, or to the side of the nest, with a diameter of 4.5 ± 0.6 cm. Clutch size varied from three ($n = 1$ nest) to four ($n = 6$ nests). The eggs were uniformly pale blue with a slight sheen. Nests with eggs were observed from 22 April to 27 May ($n = 5$), and nests with chicks were observed from 23–27 May ($n = 3$).

4.12. Food

Virtually unknown, but has been seen feeding on insect larvae.

4.13. Conservation

The total land area within the distribution range of the Tokara Leaf Warbler is about 89 km². However, the evergreen broad-leaved forests and bamboo thickets that the warbler prefers cover only 67 km², and this area may be further limited to less than 30 km² if only its major habitat, on Nakanoshima, is considered.

In the Tokara Islands, Seki et al. (2011) observed singing males in the breeding season on five Islands (Kuchinoshima, Nakanoshima, Tairajima, Suwanosejima and Akusekijima), but no birds were found on Tairajima during a later survey (Seki 2024). Breeding was confirmed only on Nakanoshima, where Higuchi & Kawaji (1989) estimated 4–5 singing males per km along two transects, and Seki (2024) estimated a stable population of on average 1.57 individuals (singing and non-singing birds) per hectare during 2001–2023. On Kuchinoshima, Suwanosejima and Akusekijima, the density of singing males was much lower than on Nakanoshima (0.02, 0.08 and 0.06 individuals/hectare; Seki 2024). The Tokara leaf Warbler is one of the commonest passerines on Nakanoshima (pers. obs.). However, the threat category could change quickly, because the species has a small population size and a geographically restricted range. In recent years, for example, a large part of the pine trees on Nakanoshima died because of the pine wilt disease, an invasive forest pest first recorded in 2015 on the island (Seki 2024). A substantial part of the warbler's breeding ground has been damaged severely due to the death of pines and the decrease of undergrowth vegetation caused by the feral goat browsing.

5. References

1. Alström, P. & Olsson, U. (1992). Taxonomic status of *Phylloscopus affinis* and *P. subaffinis*. *Bull. Br. Ornithol. Club* **112**, 111–126.
2. Alström, P. & Olsson, U. (1995). A new species of *Phylloscopus* warbler from Sichuan Province, China. *Ibis* **137**, 459–468.
3. Alström, P., Olsson, U. & Colston, P. (1997). Re-evaluation of the taxonomic status of *Phylloscopus proregulus kansuensis* Meise. *Bull. Brit. Ornithol. Club* **117**, 177–193.
4. Alström, P. & Olsson, U. (1999). The Golden-spectacled Warbler: A complex of sibling species, including a previously undescribed species. *Ibis* **141**, 545–568.
5. Alström, P. & Olsson, U. (2000). Golden-spectacled Warbler systematics. *Ibis* **142**, 495–500.
6. Alström, P. & Ranft, R. 2003. The use of sounds in avian systematics, and the importance of bird sound archives. *Bull. Brit. Ornithol. Club Supplement* **123A**, 114–135.

7. Alström, P., Ericson, P.G.P., Olsson, U., Sundberg, P. (2006). Phylogeny and classification of the avian superfamily Sylvioidea. *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* **38**, 381–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2005.05.015>
8. Alström, P., Davidson, P., Duckworth, J.W., Eames, J.C., Le, T.T., Nguyen, C., Olsson, U., Robson, C., Timmins, R.J. (2010). Description of a new species of *Phylloscopus* warbler from Vietnam and Laos. *Ibis* **152**, 145–168. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2009.00990.x>
9. Alström, P., Saitoh, T., Williams, D., Nishiumi, I., Shigeta, Y., Ueda, K., Irestedt, M., Björklund, M., Olsson, U. (2011). The Arctic Warbler *Phylloscopus borealis*—three anciently separated cryptic species revealed. *Ibis* **153**, 395–410. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2011.01116.x>
10. Alström, P., Rheindt, F.E., Zhang, R., Zhao, M., Wang, J., Zhu, X., Gwee, C.Y., Hao, Y., Ohlson, J., Jia, C., Prawiradilaga, D.M., Ericson, P.G.P., Lei, F. & Olsson, U. 2018. Complete species-level phylogeny of the leaf warbler (Aves: Phylloscopidae) radiation. *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* **126**, 141–152. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2018.03.031>)
11. Andrews, S. (2010) FastQC: A Quality Control Tool for High Throughput Sequence Data. <https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>.
12. AviList Core Team (2025) AviList: The global avian checklist, v2025. doi:10.2173/avilist.v2025.
13. Bairlein F, Alström, P., Aymí, R., Clement, P., Dyrce, A., Gargallo, G., Hawkins, F., Madge, S., Pearson, D., Svensson, L. (2006) Family Sylviidae (Warblers). In: del Hoyo J, Elliott A, Christie DA, eds. Handbook of the Birds of the World, Vol. 12 (Lynx Edicions, Barcelona), pp. 492–709.
14. Bolger AM, Lohse M, Usadel B (2014) Trimmomatic: A flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* **30**:2114–2120.
15. Bouckaert, R., Vaughan, T.G., Barido-Sottani, J., Duchêne, S., Fourment, M., Gavryushkina, A., Heled, J., Jones, G., Kühnert, D., De Maio, N., Matschiner, M., Mendes, F.K., Müller, N.F., Ogilvie, H.A., du Plessis, L., Poppinga, A., Rambaut, A., Rasmussen, D., Siveroni, I. & Drummond, A.J. (2019). BEAST 2.5: An advanced software platform for Bayesian evolutionary analysis. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **15**, e1006650. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1006650>
16. Chang, C.C., Chow, C.C., Tellier, L.C., Vattikuti, S., Purcell, S.M., Lee, J.J. (2015) Second-generation PLINK: Rising to the challenge of larger and richer datasets. *GigaScience* **4**:7.
17. Chen S, Zhou Y, Chen Y, Gu J (2018) fastp: an ultra-fast all-in-one FASTQ preprocessor. *Bioinformatics* **34**, i884–i890.
18. Charif, R.A., Waack, A.M. & Strickman, L.M. (2010). *Raven Pro 1.4 User's Manual*. Cornell Lab of Ornithology, Ithaca, NY.
19. Clement, P. (2020a). Eastern Crowned Warbler (*Phylloscopus coronatus*), version 1.0. In: del Hoyo, J., Elliott, A., Sargatal, J., Christie, D.A. & de Juana, E. (eds) *Birds of the World*. Cornell Lab of Ornithology, Ithaca, NY. <https://doi.org/10.2173/bow.eacwar1.01>
20. Clement, P. (2020b). Lemon-throated Leaf Warbler (*Phylloscopus cebuensis*), version 1.0. In: del Hoyo, J., Elliott, A., Sargatal, J., Christie, D.A. & de Juana, E. (eds) *Birds of the World*. Cornell Lab of Ornithology, Ithaca, NY. <https://doi.org/10.2173/bow.letwar1.01>

21. Clement, P. (2020c). Philippine Leaf Warbler (*Phylloscopus olivaceus*), version 1.0. In: del Hoyo, J., Elliott, A., Sargatal, J., Christie, D.A. & de Juana, E. (eds) *Birds of the World*. Cornell Lab of Ornithology, Ithaca, NY. <https://doi.org/10.2173/bow.phlwar1.01>
22. Criscuolo, A. & Gribaldo, S. (2010). BMGE (Block Mapping and Gathering with Entropy): A new software for selection of phylogenetically informative regions from multiple sequence alignments. *BMC Evol. Biol.* **10**, 210.
23. Danecek P, et al. (2011) The variant call format and VCFtools. *Bioinformatics* 27:2156–2158.
24. Darriba, D., Posada, D., Kozlov, A.M., Stamatakis, A., Morel, B. & Flouri, T. (2020). ModelTest-NG: A new and scalable tool for the selection of DNA and protein evolutionary models. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **37**, 291–294. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msz189>
25. DePristo MA, et al. (2011) A framework for variation discovery and genotyping using next-generation DNA sequencing data. *Nat Genet* 43:491–498.
26. Drummond, A.J., Ho, S.Y.W., Phillips, M.J. & Rambaut, A. (2006). Relaxed phylogenetics and dating with confidence. *PLoS Biol.* **4**, e88. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.0040088>
27. Eaton, J.A., van Balen, B., Brickle, N.W. & Rheindt, F.E. (2021). *Birds of the Indonesian Archipelago: Greater Sundas and Wallacea*, 2nd edn. Lynx Edicions, Barcelona.
28. Ericson PGP, Irestedt M, Nylander JAA, Christidis L, Joseph L, Qu, Y (2020) Parallel evolution of bower-building behavior in two groups of bowerbirds suggested by phylogenomics. *Syst Biol* 69:820–829.
29. Flouri, T., Izquierdo-Carrasco, F., Darriba, D., Aberer, A.J., Nguyen, L.-T., Minh, B.Q., von Haeseler, A. & Stamatakis, A. (2014). The Phylogenetic Likelihood Library. *Syst. Biol.* **64**, 356–362. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syu084>
30. Freeman, B.G. & Montgomery, G.A. (2017). Using song playback experiments to measure species recognition between geographically isolated populations: A comparison with acoustic trait analyses. *Auk* **134**, 857–870.
31. Fregin, S., Haase, M., Olsson, U. & Alström, P. (2012). Pitfalls in comparisons of genetic distances: A case study of the avian family Acrocephalidae. *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* **62**, 319–328.
32. Gouy, M., Guindon, S. & Gascuel, O. (2010). SeaView version 4: A multiplatform graphical user interface for sequence alignment and phylogenetic tree building. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **27**, 221–224.
33. Harada Y., Umegaki Y., Watabe Y. & Ohnishi T. (2019). Observation records of Ijima's Leaf Warblers *Phylloscopus ijimae* from Yonaguni Island and their past records from areas south of Okinawa Island, Okinawa Prefecture, southern Japan. *Strix* **35**, 1–20. (In Japanese)
34. Higuchi, H. (1973). Birds of the Izu Islands (I). Distribution and habitat of the breeding land and freshwater birds. *Tori* **22**, 14–24. (In Japanese)
35. Higuchi H, Kawaji N (1989) Ijima's willow warbler *Phylloscopus ijimae* of the Tokara Islands, a new breeding locality, in southwest Japan. *Bull Biogeogr Soc Jpn* 44:11–15.
36. International Commission of Zoological Nomenclature. (2012). Amendment of Articles 8, 9, 10, 21 and 78 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature to expand and refine methods of publication. *Zootaxa* **3450**, 1–7.

37. Irwin, D.E. (2002). Phylogeographic breaks without geographic barriers to gene flow. *Evolution* **56**, 2383–2394.
38. Irwin DE, Alcaide M, Delmore KE, Irwin JH, Owens GL (2016) Recurrent selection explains parallel evolution of genomic regions of high relative but low absolute differentiation in a ring species. *Mol Ecol* **25**, 4488–4507.
39. Jarvis, E.D., Mirarab, S., Aberer, A.J., Li, B., Houde, P., Li, C. et al. (2014). Whole-genome analyses resolve early branches in the tree of life of modern birds. *Science* **346**, 1320–1331.
40. Jiang, Z., Zang, W., Ericson, P.G.P., Song, G., Wu, S., Feng, S., Drovetski, S.V., Liu, Y., Zhang, D., Saitoh, T., Alström, P., Edwards, S.V., Lei, F. & Qu, Y. 2024. Gene flow and an anomaly zone complicate phylogenomic inference in a rapidly radiated avian family (Prunellidae). *BMC Biology* **22**,49. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12915-024-01848-7>
41. Katoh, K., Misawa, K., Kuma, K. & Miyata, T. (2002). MAFFT: A novel method for rapid multiple sequence alignment based on fast Fourier transform. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **30**, 3059–3066.
42. Katoh, K. & Standley, D.M. (2013). MAFFT multiple sequence alignment software version 7: Improvements in performance and usability. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **30**, 772–780. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/mst010>
43. Kozlov, A.M., Darriba, D., Flouri, T., Morel, B. & Stamatakis, A. (2019). RAxML-NG: A fast, scalable, and user-friendly tool for maximum likelihood phylogenetic inference. *Bioinformatics* **35**, 4453–4455.
44. Kumar, S. et al. 2025. MEGA 12.1. <https://megasoftware.net/>
45. Li, H. (2011). A statistical framework for SNP calling, mutation discovery, association mapping and population genetical parameter estimation from sequencing data. *Bioinformatics*, 27(21), 2987-2993.
46. Li, H. (2013). Aligning sequence reads, clone sequences and assembly contigs with BWA-MEM. arXiv preprint arXiv:1303.3997.
47. Li H, Durbin R (2009). Fast and accurate short read alignment with Burrows–Wheeler transform. *Bioinformatics* 25:1754–1760.
48. Li, H., Handsaker, B., Wysoker, A., Fennell, T., Ruan, J., Homer, N., ... & 1000 Genome Project Data Processing Subgroup. (2009). The Sequence Alignment/Map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics* **25**, 2078–2079.
49. Lundberg M, et al. (2023). Extreme genomic differentiation driven by a chromosomal inversion in willow warblers. *Nat Commun* **14**:5162.
50. Martens, J. (1988). *Phylloscopus borealoides* Portenko—ein verkannter Laubsänger der Ost-Paläarktis. *J. Ornithol.* **129**, 343–351.
51. Martens, J. (2010). A preliminary review of the leaf warbler genera *Phylloscopus* and *Seicercus*. *Brit. Ornithol. Club Occasional Publ.* **5**, 41–116.
52. Martens, J., Eck, S., Päckert, M. & Sun, Y.-H. (1999). The Golden-spectacled Warbler *Seicercus burkii*—a species swarm (Aves: Passeriformes: Sylviidae), part 1. *Zool. Abh. Mus. Dresden* **50**, 281–327.
53. Morel, B., Kozlov, A.M. & Stamatakis, A. (2019). ParGenes: A tool for massively parallel model selection and phylogenetic tree inference on thousands of genes. *Bioinformatics* **35**, 1771–1773. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty839>
54. Narasimhan V, et al. (2016) BCFtools/RoH: A hidden Markov model approach for detecting autozygosity. *Bioinformatics* **32**,1749–1751.

55. Ng, N.S.R., Prawiradilaga, D.M., Ng, E.Y., Suparno, Ashari, H., Trainor, C., ... & Rheindt, F.E. (2018) A striking new species of leaf warbler from the Lesser Sundas as uncovered through morphology and genomics. *Sci. Rep.* 8:15646.
56. Olsson, U., Alström, P., Colston, P.R. (1993). A new species of *Phylloscopus* warbler from Hainan Island, China. *Ibis* **135**, 2–7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.1993.tb02803.x>
57. The Ornithological Society of Japan (2012). *Checklist of Japanese Birds*. 7th revised edition. Ornithological Society of Japan, Sanda.
58. Päckert, M., Martens, J., Sun, Y.-H. & Veith, M. (2004). The radiation of the *Seicercus burkii* complex and its congeners (Aves: Sylviidae): Molecular genetics and bioacoustics. *Org. Divers. Evol.* **4**, 341–364.
59. Päckert, M., Blume, C., Sun, Y.-H., Wei, L. & Martens, J. (2009). Acoustic differentiation reflects mitochondrial lineages in Blyth's leaf warbler and white-tailed leaf warbler complexes (Aves: *Phylloscopus reguloides*, *Phylloscopus davisoni*). *Biol. J. Linn. Soc.* **96**, 584–600.
60. Pyle, P., Howell, S.N.G., Yunick, R.P. & DeSante, D.F. (1987). *Identification Guide to North American Passerines*. Slate Creek Press, CA.
61. Rambaut, A., Drummond, A.J., Xie, D., Baele, G. & Suchard, M.A. (2018). Posterior summarization in Bayesian phylogenetics using Tracer 1.7. *Syst. Biol.* **67**, 901–904. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syy032>
62. Rambaut, A. (2018). FigTree v1.4.4. Available at: <http://tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/software/figtree/>
63. Rheindt, F.E. (2006). Splits galore: the revolution in Asian leaf warbler systematics. *BirdingASIA* **5**, 25–39.
64. Rheindt, F.E., Prawiradilaga, D.M., Ashari, H., Suparno, Gwee, C.Y., Lee, G.W., ... & Ng, N.S. (2020) A lost world in Wallacea: Description of a montane archipelagic avifauna. *Science* **367**,167–170.
65. Rheindt, F.E., Bouchard, P., Pyle, R.L., Welter-Schultes, F., Aescht, E., Ah Yong, S.T., Ballerio, A., Bourgoïn, T., Ceriaco, L.M.P., Dmitriev, D., Evenhuis, N., Grygier, M.J., Harvey, M.S., Kottelat, M., Kluge, N., Krell, F.-T., Kojima, J.-i., Kullander, S.O., Lucinda, P., Lyal, C.H.C., Scioscia, C.L., Whitmore, D., Yanega, Z.-Q. Zhang, H.-Z. Zhou & Pape, T. (2023). Tightening the requirements for species diagnoses would help integrate DNA-based descriptions in taxonomic practice. *PLoS Biol.* **21**, e3002251.
66. Richman, A.D. (1996). Ecological diversification and community structure in the Old World leaf warblers (genus *Phylloscopus*): a phylogenetic perspective. *Evolution* **50**, 2461–2470.
67. Saitoh, T., Shigeta, Y. & Ueda, K. (2008). Morphological differences among populations of the Arctic Warbler with some intraspecific taxonomic notes. *Ornithol. Sci.* **7**, 135–142.
68. Singh, A., Gupta, S.K., Alström, P., Mohan, D., Hooper, D.H., Kumar, R.S., Bhatt, D., Singh, P. & Price, T.D. (2020). Taxonomy of cryptic species in the *Cyornis rubeculoides* complex in the Indian subcontinent. *Ibis* **162**, 924–935.
69. Seki, S.-I., Takagi, S., Nakamura, N., Crystal, F. (2011) Avifauna of the Tokara Islands, northern Ryukyu Archipelago. *Bull FFPRI* **10**,183–229. (In Japanese)
70. Seki, S.-I. (2024) Breeding distribution of the isolated Iijima's leaf warbler population in the Tokara Islands and its ecological, morphological, and genetic characteristics. *J Yamashina Inst Ornithol* **56**, 33–50. (In Japanese)

71. Sokolovskis, K., Bianco, G., Willemoes, M., Solovyeva, D., Bensch, S. & Åkesson, S. (2018). Ten grams and 13,000 km on the wing—route choice in willow warblers *Phylloscopus trochilus yakutensis* migrating from Far East Russia to East Africa. *Mov. Ecol.* **6**, 20.
72. Spottiswoode, C.N., Stryjewski, K.F., Quader, S., Colebrook-Robjent, J.F.R. & Sorenson, M.D. (2011). Ancient host specificity within a single species of brood parasitic bird. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **108**, 17738–17742.
73. Stejneger, L. (1892). Two additions to the Japanese avifauna, including description of a new species. *Proc. U.S. Natl. Mus.* **15**, 371–372.
74. Stoltz, M., Baeumer, B., Bouckaert, R., Fox, C., Hiscott, G., Bryant, D. (2021). Bayesian inference of species trees using diffusion models. *Syst Biol* **70**, 145–161.
75. Ticehurst, C.B. (1938). *A Systematic review of the Genus Phylloscopus (Willow-Warblers or Leaf-Warblers)*. Trustees of the British Museum, London.
76. Ueta, M. & Sato, N. (2021). The third dataset of The Breeding Bird Atlas of Tokyo (2016 to 2021). *Bird. Res.* **17**, R11–R14. (In Japanese) <https://www.bird-atlas.jp/news/bbstokyo2016-21.pdf>
77. Uyen, M. & Mirarab, S. (2018). TreeShrink: Fast and accurate detection of outlier long branches in collections of phylogenetic trees. *BMC Genomics* **19** (Suppl. 5), 272.
78. Van Der Auwera, G.A., O’Connor, B.D. (2020). *Genomics in the Cloud: Using Docker, GATK, and WDL in Terra*. O’Reilly Media.
79. Williamson, K. (1967). *Identification for Ringers: The genus Phylloscopus*, 2nd edn. British Trust for Ornithology, Tring, Herts.
80. Wu L, Dang J, Tang L, Cheng Y, Song G, Sun Y-h, Martens J, Päckert M, Alström P, Zhang D, Jia C, Lei F (2023) Limited song-mixing without recent gene flow in a contact zone between two songbird species. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **40**: msad053. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msad053>
81. Zhang, D., She, H., Wang, S., Wang, H., Li, S., Cheng, Y., Song, G., Jia, C., Qu, Y., Rheindt, F.E., Olsson, U., Alström, P. & Lei, F.-M. (2024). Phylogenetic conflict between species tree and maternally inherited gene trees in a clade of *Emberiza* buntings. *Syst. Biol.* **73**: 279–289. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syad078>
82. Zhang, D., Tang, L., Cheng, Y., Yao, H., Xiong, Y., Song, G., Qu, Y., Rheindt, F.E., Alström, P., Jia, C. & Lei, F. (2019). “Ghost introgression” as a cause of deep mitochondrial divergence in a bird species complex. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **36**, 2375–2386.
83. Zhang, C. & Mirarab, S. (2022). Weighting by gene tree uncertainty improves accuracy of quartet-based species trees. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **39**, msac215.

5. SI Appendix Tables

Measurement	Factor loading		
	PC1	PC2	PC3
Natural wing length (NW)	0.5133	-0.3791	-0.2533
Tail length (TAIL)	0.4866	-0.2051	-0.5538
Tarsus length (TAR)	0.4684	0.3246	0.3631
Nostril head length (NAL)	0.4098	-0.2973	0.6876
Total head length (TH)	0.3353	0.7877	-0.1562
Variance explained (%)	49.67	19.08	16.22
Cumulative variance (%)	49.67	68.75	84.97

SI Appendix Table S1. Principal component scores for the three principal component axes based on five morphometrics.

	Tokara (<i>n</i> = 35)	Izu (<i>n</i> = 15)	
Natural wing length (NW)	61.4 ± 1.95 (56.3–64.0)	62.3 ± 2.2 (57.7–65.6)	N.S.
Tail length (TAIL)	45.1 ± 1.8 (39.5–47.8)	46.2 ± 2.0 (43.0–49.0)	N.S.
Tarsus length (TAR)	18.4 ± 0.5 (17.2–19.3)	19.1 ± 0.4 (18.2–19.8)	<i>p</i> < 0.001
Bill length (BL)	7.9 ± 0.4 (<i>n</i> = 28) (7.2–8.8)	8.1 ± 0.4 (7.5–8.9)	N.S.
Total head length (TH)	30.3 ± 0.6 (29.1–31.6)	30.6 ± 0.4 (29.8–31.3)	<i>p</i> < 0.05
Body weight (g) (BW)	9.6 ± 0.5 (<i>n</i> = 34) (8.8–10.6)	9.9 ± 0.5 (9.0–11.0)	N.S.
Wing formula *	8=7>6>5>9>4>3>2>1 >10 (<i>n</i> = 3) 8>7>6>5>9>4>3>2>1 >10 (<i>n</i> = 4)	8=7>6>5>9>4>3>2>1>10 (<i>n</i> = 2) 8>7>6>5>9>4>3>2>1>10 (<i>n</i> = 1) 7>8>6>5>9>4>3>2>1>10 (<i>n</i> = 2)	

SI Appendix Table S2. Measurements (mean ± SD, range) and wing formula of *P. ijimae* from Tokara and Izu Islands. Sample size of measurements in parentheses after mean ± SD when differing from the main number. All measurements in mm. Primaries numbered descendently, i.e. from the inner towards the outer.

	Tokara (<i>n</i> = 29)	Izu (<i>n</i> = 33)	t60	P
Low Freq (kHz)	3.473 ± 0.338	4.087 ± 0.493	5.650	<0.001
High Freq (kHz)	7.482 ± 0.355	8.401 ± 0.484	8.423	<0.001
Center Freq (kHz)	5.258 ± 0.219	5.528 ± 0.374	3.406	0.001
Delta Freq (kHz)	4.009 ± 0.254	4.313 ± 0.431	3.325	0.002
BW 90% (kHz)	2.010 ± 0.241	2.532 ± 0.402	6.096	<0.001
Delta Time (s)	1.332 ± 0.216	1.201 ± 0.139	-2.880	0.006
Duration 90% (s)	0.811 ± 0.100	0.589 ± 0.092	-9.068	<0.001
Avg Entropy (bits)	2.626 ± 0.149	2.968 ± 0.203	7.470	<0.001
No. syllables	8.450 ± 1.555	5.385 ± 0.800	-9.936	<0.001
No. elements	1.000 ± 0.000	1.861 ± 0.293	15.830	<0.001
No. syll./s BW90	10.506 ± 1.807	9.349 ± 1.801	-2.520	0.014
No. syll./s Delta	6.335 ± 0.491	4.486 ± 0.447	-15.509	<0.001

SI Appendix Table S3. Comparison of Type I songs between *P. ijimae* from Tokara and Izu Islands. Independent sample t-test was used to compare differences between groups for each variable.

	PC1	PC2	PC3
Low Freq (kHz)	0.96	0.091	-0.078
High Freq (kHz)	0.828	-0.008	0.498
Center Freq (kHz)	0.751	0.264	0.265
Delta Freq (kHz)	0.043	-0.136	0.911
BW 90% (kHz)	0.277	-0.227	0.804
Delta Time (s)	0.041	0.864	-0.062
Dur. 90% (s)	-0.738	0.469	-0.084
Avg Entropy (bits)	0.215	-0.522	0.58
No. syll.	-0.4	0.867	-0.25
No. el.	0.743	-0.499	0.204
No. syll./s BW90	0.241	0.757	-0.243
No. syll./s Delta	-0.632	0.59	-0.296
Eigenvalue	4.012	3.31	2.399
% Variance explained	33.43	27.585	19.993

SI Appendix Table S4. Principal Component Analysis with varimax rotation of the 12 song variables in SI Appendix Table S3 for Type 1 songs generated 3 principal components (Eigenvalues > 1) that explained 81.0 % of the variance.

	Group Membership	Predicted Group Membership	
		Izu	Tokara
Number of individuals	Tokara	0	29
	Izu	32	1
%	Tokara	0	100
	Izu	97	3

SI Appendix Table S5. Rate of correct classification was 98.4 % in forward stepwise Discriminant Function Analysis with leave-one-out cross validation of Type 1 songs based on the 12 variables in SI Appendix Table S3.

	Tokara (<i>n</i> = 20)	Izu (<i>n</i> = 25)	t43	P
Low Freq (kHz)	2.186 ± 0.593	2.497 ± 0.233	2.405	0.021
High Freq (kHz)	6.995 ± 0.554	7.662 ± 0.708	3.449	0.001
Center Freq (kHz)	4.745 ± 0.393	4.574 ± 0.351	-1.540	0.131
Delta Freq (kHz)	4.809 ± 0.375	5.165 ± 0.744	1.952	0.058
BW 90% (kHz)	2.284 ± 0.251	2.363 ± 0.373	0.808	0.424
Delta Time (s)	1.141 ± 0.298	1.164 ± 0.22	0.308	0.759
Dur. 90% (s)	0.812 ± 0.225	0.731 ± 0.162	-1.398	0.169
Avg Entropy (bits)	2.582 ± 0.163	3.010 ± 0.245	6.699	<0.001
No. syll.	2.940 ± 1.341	3.259 ± 0.607	1.062	0.294
No. el.	1.350 ± 0.489	1.400 ± 0.500	0.336	0.738
No. syll./s BW90	3.523 ± 1.039	4.572 ± 0.912	3.604	0.001
No. syll./s Delta	2.513 ± 0.833	2.832 ± 0.465	1.630	0.110

SI Appendix Table S6. Comparison of Type 2 songs between *P. ijimae* from Tokara and Izu Islands. Independent sample t-test was used to compare differences between groups for each variable (significant differences are highlighted in bold).

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
Low Freq (kHz)	0.241	-0.014	0.22	0.703
High Freq (kHz)	0.089	0.089	0.894	0.381
Center Freq (kHz)	-0.089	0.08	0.144	0.755
Delta Freq (kHz)	-0.072	0.112	0.866	-0.07
BW 90% (kHz)	0.117	0.21	0.424	-0.531
Delta Time (s)	0.069	0.93	0.163	-0.011
Dur 90% (s)	-0.028	0.972	0.056	0.053
Avg Entropy (bits)	0.418	-0.021	0.409	-0.527
No. syll.	0.699	0.68	0.071	0.004
No. el.	-0.413	-0.247	0.181	-0.412
No. syll./s BW90	0.948	-0.092	0.091	-0.034
No. syll./s Delta	0.934	0.104	-0.025	0.016
Eigenvalue	2.703	2.424	2.043	1.948
% Variance explained	22.527	20.204	17.022	16.231

SI Appendix Table S7. Principal Component Analysis with varimax rotation of the 12 song variables for Type 2 songs in SI Appendix Table S6 generated 4 principal components (Eigenvalues > 1) that explained 76% of the variance.

	Group Membership	Predicted Group Membership	
		Izu	Tokara
Number of individuals	Tokara	2	18
	Izu	23	2
%	Tokara	10	90
	Izu	92	8

SI Appendix Table S8. Rate of correct classification was 91% in forward stepwise Discriminant Function Analysis with leave-one-out cross validation of Type 2 songs based on the 12 variables in SI Appendix Table S6.

	Tokara (<i>n</i> = 5)	Izu (<i>n</i> = 6)	<i>t</i>₉	<i>P</i>
Low Freq (kHz)	3.965 ± 0.129	3.932 ± 0.049	-0.590	0.569
High Freq (kHz)	5.519 ± 0.302	5.270 ± 0.140	-1.811	0.104
Center Freq (kHz)	4.785 ± 0.212	4.652 ± 0.099	-1.384	0.200
Delta Freq (kHz)	1.554 ± 0.21	1.339 ± 0.125	-2.113	0.064
BW 90% (kHz)	0.779 ± 0.126	0.656 ± 0.043	-2.263	0.050
Delta Time (s)	0.186 ± 0.018	0.200 ± 0.034	0.844	0.421
Dur 90% (s)	0.125 ± 0.014	0.135 ± 0.019	1.003	0.342

SI Appendix Table S9. Comparison of call features between Tokara and Izu Islands (independent sample t-test).

Variables	PC1	PC2	PC3
Low Freq (kHz)	0.741	-0.439	-0.342
High Freq (kHz)	0.953	-0.226	0.198
Center Freq (kHz)	0.93	-0.273	-0.002
Delta Freq (kHz)	0.883	-0.088	0.413
BW 90% (kHz)	0.857	-0.14	0.242
Delta Time (s)	-0.118	0.946	-0.128
Dur. 90% (s)	-0.332	0.918	-0.117
Avg Entropy	0.198	-0.17	0.893
Eigenvalue	4	2.113	1.212

SI Appendix Table S10. Eigenvalues and factor loadings for Principal Components Analysis of calls between Tokara and Izu.

Extremely small or no morphological differences, pronounced song differences	
<i>P. forresti</i> – <i>P. kansuensis</i>	Alström et al. (1997), Wu et al. (2023)
<i>P. emeiensis</i> – <i>P. claudiae</i>	Alström & Olsson (1995)
<i>P. tenellipes</i> – <i>P. borealoides</i>	Martens (1988)
<i>P. borealis</i> – <i>P. examinandus</i> – <i>P. xanthodryas</i>	Saitoh et al. (2008), Alström et al. (2011)
<i>P. burkii</i> – <i>P. tephrocephalus</i> – <i>P. soror</i> – <i>P. omeiensis</i> – <i>P. valentini</i> – <i>P. whistleri</i>	Alström & Olsson (1999), Martens et al. (1999), Alström & Olsson (2000), Päckert et al. (2004)
Distinct morphological differences, very slight or no song differences	
<i>P. hainanus</i> – <i>P. xanthoschistos</i> – <i>P. ogilviegranti</i>	Olsson et al. (1993), Päckert et al. (2009)
<i>P. castaniceps</i> – <i>P. grammiceps</i> – <i>P. montis</i>	Eaton et al. (2021)
<i>P. rotiensis</i> – <i>P. sarasinorum</i> – <i>P. nesophilus</i> – <i>P. presebytes</i> – <i>P. floresianus</i>	Ng et al. (2018), Eaton et al. (2021)

SI Appendix Table S11. Examples of *Phylloscopus* species with varying divergence in morphology and song.

Sister species		<i>F_{ST}</i>	Reference
<i>P. griseolus</i>	<i>P. affinis</i>	0.37–0.38	Zhang et al. (2019)
<i>P. forresti</i>	<i>P. kansuensis</i>	0.1035–0.0996 (sympatry and allopatry, respectively)	Wu et al. (2023)
<i>P. trochiloides viridanus</i>	<i>P. plumbeitarsus</i>	0.3335 on autosomes and 0.5183 on the Z chromosome	Irwin et al. (2016)
<i>P. collybita abietinus</i>	<i>P. tristis</i>	0.220 ± 0.064 for allopatric and 0.099 ± 0.038 for sympatric populations	Talla et al. (2017)

SI Appendix Table S12. Levels of differentiation between different clades in Phylloscopidae.

Sample ID	Museum ID	Locality	Collecting date	Sex	Age	Measured by
2010-0831		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	23 Jun 2010	M	Ad	Y. Shigeta
2017-0837	YIO-76875	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	10 Jun 2017	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2017-0859		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	10 Jun 2017		Ad	
2017-0838	YIO-76774	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	10 Jun 2017	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2017-0861		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	11 Jun 2017		Ad	
2017-0862		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	12 Jun 2017	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2017-0863		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	12 Jun 2017	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2017-0865		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	12 Jun 2017	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2017-0866		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	14 Jun 2017	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2017-0867		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	14 Jun 2017	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2016-2337		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	23 Jun 2016	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
1F26406		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	25 May 2014	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26408		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	25 May 2014	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26409		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	25 May 2014	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26410		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	27 May 2014	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26411		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	27 May 2014	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26413		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	15 April 2015	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26442		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	26 May 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26443		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	27 May 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26444		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	27 May 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26445		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	27 May 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F26446		Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	28 May 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki

1F2644 7	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	28 May 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2645 2	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	16 April 2017	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2645 6	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	18 April 2017	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2646 1	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	29 May 2017	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 0	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	25 April 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 1	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	25 April 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 2	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	25 April 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 4	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	25 April 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 5	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	26 April 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 6	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	23 May 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 7	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	25 May 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 8	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	26 May 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2649 9	Nakanoshima I., Tokara Is., Kagoshima, Japan	26 May 2023	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
2010- 0885	Miyakejima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	6 July 2010	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2010- 0886	Miyakejima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	6 July 2010	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2010- 0887	Miyakejima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	6 July 2010	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2024- 1304	Miyakejima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	5 July 2020	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2024- 1305	Miyakejima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	5 July 2020	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
2021- 2271	Miyakejima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	30 Jun 2021	M	Ad	T. Saitoh
No Ring	Hachijojima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	17 July 2014	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2644 8	Mikurajima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	7 Jun 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2645 0	Miyakejima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	14 July 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2645 1	Miyakejima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	14 July 2016	M	Ad	S-I. Seki

1F2646 2	Aogashima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	14 Jun 2017	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2646 3	Aogashima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	14 Jun 2017	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2646 4	Hachijojima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	17 Jun 2017	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2646 5	Hachijojima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	17 Jun 2017	M	Ad	S-I. Seki
1F2646 6	Hachijojima I., Izu Is., Tokyo, Japan	17 Jun 2017	M	Ad	S-I. Seki

SI Appendix Table S13. 50 adult males measured in the field from Tokara Is. (Nakanoshima Is.) and Izu Is., Japan between 2010 and 2023.

Species	Lab Id. No.	Museum/field No.	Sex	Locality	Date	Accession No.
Whole genome						
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5649	YIO-1996-0250/YIO-62744	f	Miyakejima	5 Aug 1993	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5645/ U5707	YIO-2010-0885	m	Miyakejima	6 July 2010	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5646/ U5708	YIO-2010-0886	m	Miyakejima	6 July 2010	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5709	YIO-2010-0887	f	Miyakejima	6 July 2010	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5710	YIO ring No. 1D36521	m	Miyakejima	5 July 2020	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5711	YIO ring No. 1D36522	m	Miyakejima	5 July 2020	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5147	Field No. PA20170610-1	m	Nakanoshima	10 June 2017	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5148	Field No. PA20170610-2 YIO-76774 (holotype)	m	Nakanoshima	10 June 2017	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5149	Field No. PA20170610-3 YIO-76875 (paratype)	m	Nakanoshima	10 June 2017	PRJEB105759

<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5150	Field No. PA20170611-4	m	Nakanoshima	11 June 2017	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5151	Field No. PA20170612-5	m	Nakanoshima	12 June 2017	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5152	Field No. PA20170612-6	m	Nakanoshima	12 June 2017	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5153	Field No. PA20170612-7	m	Nakanoshima	12 June 2017	PRJEB105759
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5154	Field No. PA20170614-8	m	Nakanoshima	14 June 2017	PRJEB105759
<i>P. coronatus</i>	P28020_341	UWBM 75276		Primorsky kray, Russia		PRJEB105759
<i>P. coronatus</i>	P28020_234	UWBM 71710		Primorsky kray, Russia		PRJEB105759
<i>P. coronatus</i>	IOZ 16349	IOZ SX11090		Shaanxi Prov., China		PRJEB105759
<i>P. coronatus</i>	IOZ 16348	IOZ SX11089		Shaanxi Prov., China		PRJEB105759
<i>P. coronatus</i>	IOZ 16323	IOZ SX11064		Shaanxi Prov., China		PRJEB105759
<i>P. cebuensis</i>	P28021_128	VH A835 2052		Isabella, Luzon, Philippines		MH079253
<i>P. olivaceus</i>	U1675	FMNH 357489		Mt Kitanglad, Mindanao, Philippines		MH079322
<i>P. olivaceus</i>	U1676	FMNH 357490		Mt Kitanglad, Mindanao, Philippines		MH079323
Cytochrome b						
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5649	YIO-1996- 0250/YIO-62744	f	Miyakejima	5 Aug 1993	GB: PX738499
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U1364	YIO ring No. 1A-85532	f	Miyakejima	19 July 2006	GB: PX738490
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U1365	YIO ring No. 1A-85534	m	Miyakejima	19 July 2006	GB: PX738491
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U1366	YIO ring No. 1A-85537	m	Miyakejima	20 July 2006	GB: PX738492
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U1367	YIO ring No. 1A-85535	?	Miyakejima	19 July 2006	GB: PX738493
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U1368	YIO ring No. 1A-85533	m	Miyakejima	19 July 2006	GB: MH079296

<i>P. ijimae</i>	U1369	YIO ring No. 1A-85536	m	Miyakejima	19 July 2006	GB: PX738494
<i>P. ijimae</i>	1996- 0249	YIO 62743	f	Miyakejima		GB: MH079296
<i>P. ijimae</i>	2009- 0563	YIO 2009-0563	m	Miyakejima		GB: PX738495
<i>P. ijimae</i>	2011- 1043	YIO 2011-1043	f?	Miyakejima		GB: PX738498
<i>P. ijimae</i>			?	Miyakejima		GB: Y10741
<i>P. ijimae</i>			?	Miyakejima		GB: L77141
<i>P. ijimae</i>			?	Miyakejima		GB: LC541446
<i>P. ijimae</i>	2010- 0855	YIO 2010-0855	m	Miyakejima	25 June 2010	GB: PX738500
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5646/ U5708	YIO-2010-0886	m	Miyakejima	6 July 2010	GB: PX738496
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5709	YIO-2010-0887	f	Miyakejima	6 July 2010	GB: PX738497
<i>P. ijimae</i>	2014- 0830	YIO 2014-0830	?	Mikurajima, Tokyo Pref.	1 July 2014	GB: PX738487
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U1362	DZUG U1362	?	Kagoshima, Kagoshima Pref.	2 Sept. 2005	GB: PX738488
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U1363	DZUG U1363	?	Kagoshima, Kagoshima Pref.	20 Aug. 2006	GB: PX738489
<i>P. ijimae</i>			?	Nakanoshima*		GB: L77142
<i>P. ijimae</i>		2010-0831	m	Nakanoshima	23 June 2010	GB: PX738511
<i>P. ijimae</i>		2010-0869	m	Nakanoshima	25 June 2010	GB: PX738512
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U3992		?	Nakanoshima		GB: PX738501
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5147	Field No. PA20170610-1	m	Nakanoshima	10 June 2017	GB: PX738502
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5148	Field No. PA20170610-2 YIO-76774 (holotype)	m	Nakanoshima	10 June 2017	GB: PX738503
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5149	Field No. PA20170610-3 YIO-76875 (paratype)	m	Nakanoshima	10 June 2017	GB: PX738504

<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5150	Field No. PA20170611-4	m	Nakanoshima	11 June 2017	GB: PX738505
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5151	Field No. PA20170612-5	m	Nakanoshima	12 June 2017	GB: PX738506
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5152	Field No. PA20170612-6	m	Nakanoshima	12 June 2017	GB: PX738507
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5153	Field No. PA20170612-7	m	Nakanoshima	12 June 2017	GB: PX738508
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5154	Field No. PA20170614-8	m	Nakanoshima	14 June 2017	GB: PX738509
<i>P. ijimae</i>	U5155	Field No. PA20170614-9	m	Nakanoshima	14 June 2017	GB: PX738510
<i>P. ijimae</i>			?	Nakanoshima		GB: LC541468
<i>P. coronatus</i>			?	Hebei, China		GB: MH079263
<i>P. olivaceus</i>			?	Mindanao, Philippines		GB: MH079322

SI Appendix Table S14. Sampling information for whole-genome resequenced samples; for samples for which only the mitochondrial cytochrome b (cytb) was obtained; and cytb sequences obtained from NCBI GenBank (GB; new sequences in bold). DZUG = Department of Zoology, University of Gothenburg (); FMNH = Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago, USA; IOZ = Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Science, Beijing, China; UWBM = University of Washington Burke Museum, Seattle, USA; VH = Zoological Institute and Museum, University of Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany (originally from collection at Vogelwarte Hiddensee); YIO = Yamashina Institute for Ornithology, Chiba, Japan; m = male, f=female. *This sample was published by Richman (1996) with a comment that “Samples of putative *P. ijimae* (Higuchi and Kawaji 1989) from S. Izu Islands, Japan were provided by H. Higuchi, Wild Bird Society of Japan”. The paper by Higuchi & Kawaji (1989) describes the discovery of the Nakanoshima population, i.e. not “S. Izu Islands”.

Sample Name	$\geq 30X$	Mean Cov.	Median
PijimaeMi-U5645	1.0%	13.5X	14.0X
PijimaeMi-U5649	2.0%	16.7X	17.0X
PijimaeMi-U5708	2.0%	18.2X	19.0X
PijimaeMi-U5709	1.0%	15.0X	16.0X
PijimaeMi-U5710	39.0%	26.3X	28.0X
PijimaeMi-U5711	1.0%	15.4X	16.0X
PijimaeNa-U5147	16.0%	23.1X	24.0X
PijimaeNa-U5148	1.0%	12.3X	12.0X
PijimaeNa-U5149	1.0%	11.2X	11.1X
PijimaeNa-U5150	1.0%	12.1X	12.0X
PijimaeNa-U5151	1.0%	12.8X	13.0X
PijimaeNa-U5152	1.0%	10.2X	10.0X
PijimaeNa-U5153	1.0%	13.2X	13.0X
PijimaeNa-U5154	1.0%	13.9X	14.0X

SI Appendix Table S15. Summary of the read mapping depth analysis for *P. ijimae* resequencing dataset (dataset #1).

Sample Name	Error rate	% Mapped	% Proper Pairs	M Total seqs	% Dups	Median
PcebuP2801_128.md.cram	6.27%	96.70%	90.00%	118.2	20.60%	11.0X
PcorU4722.md.cram	6.03%	96.30%	89.10%	194	6.90%	22.0X
PcorU4779.md.cram	6.11%	95.80%	85.20%	160.8	11.60%	16.0X
Pcoro16323A.md.cram	6.23%	96.90%	88.20%	192.4	12.40%	19.0X
Pcoro16348A.md.cram	5.98%	98.80%	94.90%	305.7	13.50%	28.0X
Pcoro16349A.md.cram	6.22%	96.90%	87.80%	212.2	12.50%	21.0X
PijiMiU5645.md.cram	5.85%	97.50%	91.20%	115.3	15.20%	12.0X
PijiMiU5649.md.cram	5.94%	95.40%	86.60%	150.1	17.00%	15.0X
PijiMiU5708.md.cram	5.95%	96.70%	89.60%	159.4	23.90%	15.0X
PijiMiU5709.md.cram	5.97%	96.50%	89.10%	132.8	15.80%	14.0X
PijiMiU5710.md.cram	5.96%	96.80%	89.90%	230.9	21.00%	23.0X
PijiMiU5711.md.cram	6.02%	96.00%	88.40%	137.1	14.30%	14.0X
PijiNaU5147.md.cram	5.94%	96.50%	89.30%	202.6	18.10%	20.0X
PijiNaU5148.md.cram	5.90%	96.70%	89.20%	107.2	14.40%	11.0X
PijiNaU5149.md.cram	5.91%	96.60%	89.30%	91.3	14.00%	9.0X
PijiNaU5150.md.cram	5.88%	97.10%	89.20%	104.4	16.60%	11.0X
PijiNaU5151.md.cram	5.91%	96.7%	88.90%	111.5	14.60%	12.0X
PijiNaU5152.md.cram	5.91%	96.7%	88.80%	89.7	14.30%	9.0X
PijiNaU5153.md.cram	5.90%	96.4%	88.70%	116	13.80%	12.0X
PijiNaU5154.md.cram	5.91%	96.40%	88.70%	116	14.30%	12.0X
PolivU1675B.md.cram	5.95%	96.60%	89.10%	132.1	22.80%	12.0X
PolivU1676.md.cram	5.88%	96.50%	89.00%	124.1	16.50%	13.0X

SI Appendix Table S16. Summary of the read mapping depth and quality analysis for *P. ijimae* resequencing dataset (dataset #2).

	π in Miyake	π in Nakanoshima	d_{XY}	F_{ST}
Mean	0.00338	0.00233	0.01114	0.74744
Min	0.00014	7e-05	0.00312	0.00692
Max	0.04551	0.04424	0.04519	0.96643
Median	0.00299	0.00211	0.01068	0.756
Standard Deviation	0.00267	0.00126	0.00303	0.08033
Variance	1e-05	0.0	1e-05	0.00645

SI Appendix Table S17. Summary statistics of nucleotide diversity (π) in *P. ijimae* populations from Izu and Tokara, and measures of genetic divergence (d_{XY}) and differentiation (F_{ST}) between populations.

Photos, GenBank (cytochrome b) and European Nucleotide Archive (genomes) numbers Nakanoshima

Individual No.	ML catalog number	GenBank	European Nucleotide Archive
1	647191542	PX738502	PRJEB105759
	647191540		
	647191537		
	647191539		
	647191536		
	647191541		
	647191538		
	647191543		
	647191535		
2			
HOLOTYPE	647191582	PX738503	PRJEB105759
	647191585		

647191579
647191578
647191581
647191587
647191576
647191584
647191580
647191589
647191586
647191588
647191583
647191577

3	PARATYPE	647191601	PX738504	PRJEB105759
		647191599		
		647191602		
		647191598		
		647191600		
		647191597		
		647191604		
		647191603		

4		647191619	PX738505	PRJEB105759
		647191614		
		647191612		
		647191618		
		647191616		
		647191613		
		647191620		
		647191617		
		647191615		

5		647191659	PX738506	PRJEB105759
		647191657		
		647191658		
		647191661		
		647191660		
		647191656		

6		647191669	PX738507	PRJEB105759
		647191670		
		647191666		
		647191668		

	647191673		
	647191667		
	647191672		
	647191671		
	647191665		
	647191663		
	647191664		
7	647191687	PX738508	PRJEB105759
	647191686		
	647191683		
	647191682		
	647191685		
	647191684		
8	647191707	PX738509	PRJEB105759
	647191711		
	647191708		
	647191706		
	647191705		
	647191709		
	647191704		
	647191703		
	647191710		
	647191730		
9	647191726	PX738510	
	647191724		
	647191725		
	647191721		
	647191722		
	647191720		
	647191731		
	647191729		
	647191723		
	647191728		
	647191719		
	647191718		
	647191727		
10	647191900		
	647191902		
	647191897		
	647191896		

647191903
647191899
647191898

Sound recordings Nakanoshima and Izu Islands

ML catalog number

- 647191929 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209. No.1
Type 1, No. 1 Type 2_1210.WAV
- 647191923 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1215. No.
2.WAV
- 647191922 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1219. No.
3.WAV
- 647191924 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1222. No.
4.WAV
- 647191952 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1229. No.
5.WAV
- 647191951 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233. No.
6.WAV
- 647191953 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1239. No.
7.WAV
- 647191965 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1242_1243.
No. 8 Type 1, No. 4 Type 2.WAV
- 647191972 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1012. No. 9
Type 1, No. 2 Type 2.WAV
- 647191975 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1024. No. 10
Type 1, No. 3 Type 2.WAV
- 647192010 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1043. No.
11.WAV
- 647191992 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1044. No.
12.WAV
- 647192003 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1048. No.
13.WAV
- 647192000 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1050. No.
14.WAV
- 647192011 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053. No. 15
Type 1, No. 5 Type 2.WAV
- 647192008 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1059. No.
16.WAV
- 647192006 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1064. No.
17.WAV
- 647191998 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1070. No.
18.WAV
- 647191999 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1071. No. 19
Type 1, No. 6 Type 2.WAV
- 647192034 Phylloscopus ijimae Song, call Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1075.
No. 20.WAV
- 647192038 Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1078. No.
21.WAV

647192035 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1079. No. 22.WAV

647192040 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1081a. No. 23 Type 1, No. 7 Type 2_1091. No. 23 Type 1.WAV

647192042 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1087. No. 24_1089. No. 24 Type 1, No. 8 Type 2.WAV

647192039 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099. No. 25 Type 1.WAV

647192036 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1101. No. 26 Type 1, No. 9 Type 2.WAV

647192043 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1103. No. 27 Type 1, No. 10 Type 2.WAV

647192037 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1107. No. 28.WAV

647192031 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1108. No. 29.WAV

647192065 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Call Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1096.WAV

647192063 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Call Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1098.WAV

647192064 *Phylloscopus ijimae* Calls, song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1015.WAV

647192107 1040_ind1_Pijimae Takema Saitoh No. 1 Type 1, No. 1 Type 2.WAV

647192105 1041_ind2_Pijimae Type 2 Takema Saitoh.WAV

647192106 1043_ind3_Pijimae Takema Saitoh No. 2 Type 2.WAV

647192103 1047_ind6_Pijimae Takema Saitoh No. 32 Type 1, No. 3 Type 2.WAV

647192101 100707_02 Takema Saitoh Type 2.WAV

647192104 Ind. 8 - 1027 Takema Saitoh No. 35.WAV

647192100 Ind. 16 - 1037 Takema Saitoh No. 34.WAV

647192102 Ind. 16 - 1038 Takema Saitoh No. 34.WAV

647356510 170510_014_Iijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda.WAV

647356514 170508_017_Iijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point2 Haruo Kuroda.WAV

647356513 160516_012_Iijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda.WAV

SI Appendix Table S18. Photos of Tokara Leaf Warbler from Nakanoshima, June 2017, with Macaulay Library (ML), GenBank and European Nucleotide Archive numbers; and previously unpublished sound recordings of Tokara Leaf Warbler and Izu Leaf Warbler analyzed in present study.

6. SI Appendix Figures

SI Appendix Figure S1. Plot of the first two principal components from a Principal Component Analysis of five morphological measurements: natural wing length (wing chord; NW), tail length (TAIL), tarsus length (TAR), bill length (BL), and total head length (TH).

SI Appendix Figure S2. Sonograms of *P. ijimae* Tokara Islands (Nakanoshima), Type I, Type II and Izu Islands (Miyakejima), Type I and Type II.

[Appended at very end of SI Appendix]

SI Appendix Figure S3. Plot of three principal components from Principal Component Analysis of 12 Type I song variables.

SI Appendix Figure S4. Plot of four principal components from Principal Component Analysis of 12 Type II song variables.

Appendix Figure S5. Sonograms of calls from Tokara and Izu Islands.

SI Appendix Figure S6. Plot of three principal components from Principal Component Analysis of 7 call variables.

SI Appendix Figure S7. Mitochondrial cytochrome b tree for all species in the family Phylloscopidae, inferred in BEAST2 (same tree as in Figure 2C in main text, but with species names visible). Posterior probabilities indicated as shades of black. In all trees, sympatric species

with divergence times comparable to or younger than the two *P. ijimae* populations (cf. Fig. 2B) are indicated by asterisks; the red asterisk at the *Seicercus* clade indicates that three of the species are sympatric on the same mountain but mainly or entirely elevationally segregated.

SI Appendix Figure S8. Phylogenetic relationships and relative divergence within the “*P. coronatus* clade”, including the two populations of *P. ijimae*, based on 15,830 genome-wide SNPs analyzed under the multispecies coalescent (SNAPPER) with equal sampling (two per species except for *P. cebuensis*, for which only one sample was available).

SI Appendix Figure S9. Mitochondrial cytochrome b tree including previously published sequences from Tokara (Nakanoshima) and Izu (Miyake, Hachijojima) Islands and sequences from birds collected on autumn migration on Kagoshima Island (highlighted in magenta), inferred in BEAST2, with *P. coronatus* and *P. olivaceus* as outgroups.

SI Appendix Figure S10. Phylogenetic tree based on whole mitochondrial genomes (16,941 base pairs), reconstructed using Bayesian Inference in BEAST2.

SI Appendix Figure S11. Genome scans for genetic diversity π (Tokara and Izu), divergence (d_{XY}), and fixation index (F_{ST}). Horizontal dashed lines indicate mean values; vertical lines mark scaffold boundaries. Elevated divergence on the first scaffold/chromosome reflects inclusion of female samples in this analysis and is interpreted as sex-specific differentiation.

SI Appendix Figure S12. Cross-validation error in ADMIXTURE analysis shows the optimal number of populations.

SI Appendix Figure S13. Site frequency spectra for two populations of the Ijima's Leaf Warbler. The distribution of minor allele counts across biallelic SNPs is shown for *P. iijimae* from Tokara (left, green) and Izu (right, orange) islands.

A

B

SI Appendix Figure S14. Demographic history inferred using Stairway Plot for two populations of *P. iljima*. Effective population size (N_e) trajectories over time are shown for Izu (top, green border) and Tokara (bottom, orange border). Solid red lines indicate median estimates; grey lines represent confidence intervals from bootstrapping.

SI Appendix Figure S15. Sound terminology. This single *strophe* (which is separated by other strophes by silent pauses) consists of six *syllables*; in this case, each syllable is made up of a single *element* (i.e. an unbroken line on the sonogram), but other syllables can consist of two or more elements.

1

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	GGATCCCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCGTA	CAAATCGTCA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	GGATNTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CNTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	GGATCTCTCC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	-----	-----	--TAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	GGATCTCTTC	TGGGCATCTG	CCTAGTCACA	CAAATTGTCA

41

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACTACACAG	CAGACACCTC
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCITATA	CACITACACAG	CAGACACTTC
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CAGGCCTACT	ACTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CAGGCCTACT	ATTAGCCATG	CACITACACAG	CAGACACCTC

81

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATCTG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCATAATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCTGGCCTTC	GCCTCCGTCG	CCCACATATG	CCGAGACGTA

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCTAACGGAG
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CAATTCGGCT	GACTAATCCG	TAACCTCCAC	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTGATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTGATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATTCG	CAACCTCCAT	GCCAATGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CAGTTCTGGCT	GACTAATCCG	CAACCTCCAC	GCCAACGGAG

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CATCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCTCCCTTCCT	CTTCATCTGC	ATCTACTTCC	ACATCGGCCG

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAA	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAA	AACAAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	AGGATTCTAC	TACGGCTCAT	ACCTAAACAA	AGAAACCTGA

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	ACTGACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	AACATTGGAG	TTGTCCCTCCT	GCTAACCCCTC	ATGGCAACTG

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCCTTCGTAGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCCTTCGTAGG	CTACGTACTTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCCTTCGTGGG	CTACGTCCCTG	CCCTTGAGGAC	AGATATCATT

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAAATTA	CAAANNNNNNN	NNNNNNNNNN
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CTGAGGCGCA	WCAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATTA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CTGAGGCGCA	ACAGTAATCA	CAAACCTATT	CTCAGCGATT

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGCG
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCGTGAGGTG
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGCG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	NNNNNNNNNN	NNNNNNNNNN	NGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCGTACATCG	GTCAAAACACT	AGTAGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCGTACATCG	GCCAAACACT	AGTGAATGA	GCATGAGGTG

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCA	ACACTAACCC	GGTTCTTTCG
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	GCTTCTCAGT	AGATAACCCC	ACACTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	GCTTCTCAGT	AGACAATCCT	ACGCTAACCC	GATTCTTTGC

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CATCCACTTC	CTTCTACCAAT	TCGTCATCGC	AGGACTAACC
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCAT	TTGGCATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CATTCACATTC	CTTCTCCCCCT	TTCTTTATCGC	AGGACTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CATTCACATTC	CTCCTACCCCT	TTGTTATCGC	AGGGCTAACC

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	TTAGTCCACC	TCACCCCTACT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CTTAGTCCACC	TCACCCCTACT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTCCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	TTAGTCCACC	TTACCCCTTCT	ACACGAAACA	GGATCAAACA

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGACA	AAATCCCATT
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	ACCCCTAGG	CATTCCACCA	GACTGCGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GACTGCGATA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGANA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	ACCCCTAGG	CATCCCATCA	GATTGTGACA	AAATCCCATT

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCACCCCTAC	TACTCTACAA	AAGACATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCACCCCTAT	TACTCCACAA	AAGATATCCT	AGGATTTGCG

601

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CTTATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CACACTAGCT	CTATTCTCCC
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CTTATACTTA	TCCTCCTTGC	CTCAGTAGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	TTCATACTGA	TTCCTCCTTGC	CGGACTGGCC	CTATTTTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	TTCATACTAA	TCCTCCTTGC	CGCATTTGCC	CTATTCTCCC

641

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCAACCTTACT	AGGNGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CACCCAGCCAA
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCAACCTTACT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCGGCCAA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGAGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CACCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CACCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CACCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CACCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CACCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCAACCTTCTT	AGGGGACCCA	GAAAAATTTCA	CGCCCGCCAA

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	TGAATGATAC
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCCCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCCCCTAGCT	ACACCGCCAC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCCCCTAGCC	ACACCACCGC	ACATTTAAACC	CGAATGATAC

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	TTCCCTAATCG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	TTCCNTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	TTCCNTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	TTCCCTAATTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	TTTCCTGTTTG	CCTACGCCAT	CCTCCGATCC	ATCCCAAAACA

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	AAC TGGG TGG	CG TACTAGCC	CTAGCCGCCT	CCGTCCCTAGT
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTAGCC	CTAGCTGCCT	CCGTCCCTGGT
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	AAC TAGGAGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	AAC TAGG CGG	CG TACTGGCC	CTAGCCGCAT	CCGTCCCTAGT

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAC TACGC
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAC TACGT
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCT CTGC	TACATA CCTC	CAAAC TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CA -ATTACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CC TATTCC TA	AT CCCCCC TAC	TACACACATC	CAAAT TACGC

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCCCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TTTGAA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	TCAA	TGACCT	TTCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	TCAA	TGACCT	TCCG	ACCTCT	CTCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	TCAA	TAACTT	TCCG	ACCTCT	ATCC	CAAATC	CTCT	TCTGAG

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CTCT	TAGTCG	CAACT	TCCCTC	GTCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	---	---	---
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCCT	TAGTCG	TAACT	TCCCTA	ATTCT	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCCT	TAGTGG	C	---	---	---	---	---
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCCT	TAGTGG	CAACT	TCCCTT	ATCC	TAACTT	GAGT	TAGGCAG

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCCT	TCATCATCAT	TGGCCAAC TA
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCAACCAGTC	AAACACCCAT	ACATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCAACCAGTC	GAACACCCAT	TCATCATCAT	CGGCCAAC TA

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	GCATCCITTC A	CCTACTTCAC	AATCAITTC TA	GTCCCTCTTC C

1001

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	CCTCGGCTC	CATCCTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	CCCTTGATC	CATTCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	-----	-----	-----	-----
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCITTAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	-----	-----	-----	-----
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCAAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCCAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCAAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	-----	-----	-----	-----
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	CCCTCGTCTC	CATCCITAGAA	AACAAGATAC	TCAAACCTCTA

1041

PcoronatusBeidaiheU3013_GB_MH079263	A
PolivaceusU1675_GB_MH079322	A
Pijimae_Hachiojima_0616_U3208_GB_MH079294	A
Pijimae_Mikurajima_Izu_Saitoh_2014-0830	A
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1361_GB_MH079295	A
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1362	A
Pijimae_Kagoshima_U1363	A
Pijimae_Miyake_U1364	A
Pijimae_Miyake_U1365	A
Pijimae_Miyake_U1366	A
Pijimae_Miyake_U1367	A
Pijimae_Miyake_U1368_GB_MH079296	A
Pijimae_Miyake_U1369	A
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2009-0563	A
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0886_U5708	A
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0887_U5709	A
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2011-1043	A
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0249	A
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_1996-0250	A
Pijimae_Izu_Helbig_GB_Y10741	A
Pijimae_Miyake_Richman_GB_L77141	-
Pijimae_Miyake_Saitoh_2010-0855	A
Pijimae_Miyake_GB_complMT_LC541446	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Richman_GB_L77142	-
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U3992	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5147	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5148	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5149	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5150	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5151	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5152	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5153	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5154	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_U5155	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0831	-
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_Saitoh_2010-0869	A
Pijimae_Nakanoshima_GB_complMT_LC541468	A

SI Appendix Figure S16. Mitochondrial cytochrome b alignment for all samples analyzed.

SI Appendix Figure S2.

A: Nakanoshima, examples of song Type I

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.1
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1242 No. 8
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1242 No. 9
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233 No. 10
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 27

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No. 1
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1215 No. 2
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1222 No. 4
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No. 8
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1012 No. 9
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1024 No. 10
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1048 No. 13
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1048 No. 14
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.15
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.16
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.17
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.18
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1071 No. 19
Phylloscopus ijimae Song, call Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1075 No. 20
Phylloscopus ijimae Song, call Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1075 No. 21
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1071 No. 24
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 25
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 27
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 28
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 29

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1219 No. 3
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1229 No. 5
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233 No. 6
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233 No. 7
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233 No. 8
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233 No. 10
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1043 No. 11
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1043 No. 12
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1043 No. 15
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.18
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 No. 23
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1071 No. 24
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 25

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1243. No. 8
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan11June2017 NAK2017_1012 No. 9
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233 No. 10
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 No. 15
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 No. 22
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 No. 23
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 25
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1081a No. 27

The above one is considered a repetition of a single element, as it shows up as such when the contrast is increased further.

- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.1
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1242 No. 8
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan11June2017 NAK2017_1012 No. 9
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233 No. 10
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1233 No. 18
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1071 No. 19
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 No. 23
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1071 No. 24
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 25
- Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1099 No. 26

The above one is considered a repetition of a single element, as it shows up as such when the contrast is increased further.

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.1
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1024 No. 10
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 No.15
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 No. 19
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1089 No. 24
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1089 No. 27

The above one is considered a repetition of a single element, as it shows up as such when the contrast is increased further.

The above one is considered a repetition of a single element, as it shows up as such when the contrast is increased further.

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1103 No. 27

The one above is considered to consist of a single repeated element, as it shows up as such when the contrast is increased further. **Borderline between Type 1 and Type 2.**

Combination of two of above syllables

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1070 No. 18 (5)

B: Nakanoshima, examples of song Type II

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 TYPE 2 and 1

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 10June2017 NAK2017_1209 TYPE 1 and 2

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1024 No. 10
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1071 No. 19
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1081a No. 23
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1089 No. 24
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1101 No. 26
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1103 No. 27
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1012

The one above is considered to consist of a single repeated element, as it shows up as such when the contrast is increased further. **Borderline between Type 1 and 2.**

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1089 No. 24

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1081a No. 23

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1024 No. 10
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 11June2017 NAK2017_1242 No. 8
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1081a No. 23
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1089 No. 24
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1101 No. 26
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 14June2017 NAK2017_1081a No. 23 **TYPE 2**
and 1

Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 TYPE 2 and 1
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 TYPE 2 and 1
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 TYPE 2 and 1
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053 TYPE 2 and 1
Phylloscopus ijimae Song Nakanoshima, Japan 12June2017 NAK2017_1053

C: Miyakejima, examples of song Type I

XC465461

ML619656959 = ML619656969

ML149521431

170508_017_Iijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point2 Haruo Kuroda

1040_ind1_Pijimae
XC192198
XC920559
XC410355
XC285851
XC285843
XC285845 = XC285846
XC155766
XC410354 = XC410355
XC172361
XC172362
ML586676401 = ML586944541
ML449449991
ML619656969
1043_ind3_Pijimae
1047_ind6_Pijimae
P. ijimae Miyake Takema 2020 - ind1 1019
P. ijimae Miyake Takema 2020 - ind6 1025
P. ijimae Miyake Takema 2020 - ind8 1027
170510_014_Iijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda
160516_012_Iijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda

1040_ind1_Pijimae

XC749101

XC749102

XC285904

ML619656969

ML279704791

P. ijimae Miyake Takema 2020 - ind16

170508_017_ijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point2 Haruo Kuroda

XC749102
XC749104
XC285851
ML279704791
ML619656969

XC749103
XC285851
170508_017_lijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point2 Haruo Kuroda
XC749102
XC285904
ML586676401 (not measured, but clearly this type)

XC749102

Phylloscopus ijimae song Japan Izu Is Miyake Is 15-5-75 T Kabaya

one element/syllable

160516_012_ijjima_Song_Miyake Isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda (5)

D: Miyakejima, examples of song Type II

1040_ind1_Pijimae

1041_ind2_Pijimae

ML586676401

ML586944541

1052_ind11_Pijimae

P. ijimae Miyake Takema 2020 - ind 5 1024

XC49102

XC285847

ML586676401

ML586944541

1040_ind1_Pijimae

XC285851

XC749102

1043_ind3_Pjima
1047_ind6_Pijimae
1049_ind8_Pijimae

1047_ind6_Pijimae
P. ijimae Miyake Takema 100707_02

XC285904

170510_014_ijima_Song_Miyake isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda

170510_014_lijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda

1040_ind1_Pijimae

160516_012_lijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda

170508_017_lijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point2 Haruo Kuroda

P. ijimae Miyake Takema 2020 - ind 16 1038

170510_014_lijima_Song_Miyake isl Point3 Haruo Kuroda
ML619656969

ML279704791

170508_017_lijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point2 Haruo Kuroda

170508_017_lijima_Song_Miyake Isl Point2 Haruo Kuroda

ML279704791

Phylloscopus ijimae song Japan Izu Is Miyake Is 15-5-75 T Kabaya

XC749102 TYPE 2 and 1

SI Appendix Figure S2. Sonograms of *P. ijimae* Tokara Islands (Nakanoshima), Type I, Type II and Izu Islands (Miyakejima), Type I and Type II.